

SECReTOUR
Sustainable Creative Tourism

Deliverable

Report on alternative and hybrid business models

Literature Review and Case Examples

Deliverable no.: D2.1

Lead Beneficiary: CBS

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Dissemination Level: Public

Due Date: 29 February 2025

Delivery Date: 19 March 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15254190

Funded by
the European Union

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER

101132584

PROJECT ACRONYM

SECReTour

PROJECT TITLE

Sustainable, Engaging and CREative Tourism as a driver for a better future in rural and remote areas

FUNDED UNDER

Culture, creativity and inclusive society

START DATE

01.03.2024

PROJECT COORDINATORProf. José María Martín Civantos
Universidad de Granada - Spain**PROJECT WEBSITE**<https://secretourproject.eu/>**2024 SECReTour**

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Version history

Change Log			
Version	Date	Author	Reason for Change
1.0	26/02/2025	María Rodríguez Ayerbe Esben Rahbek Gjerdrum Pedersen (CBS)	First draft
1.1	03/03/2025	Matevz Straus (ARCTUR)	Internal review- comments and suggestions
1.2	06/03/2025	María Teresa Bonet García (UGR)	Project manager- suggestions
1.3	17/03/2025	Viktor Smith and Carsten Jacob Humlebæk (CBS)	Final version

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Executive summary

In the last decade, there has been a rapidly growing interest in business model thinking and relevant subdomains (e.g. entrepreneurial business models, digital business models, and sustainable business models). However, only few attempts have been made to examine how the business model perspective can be used to understand the organisational architectures of cultural offerings (hereinafter referred to as 'cultural business model').

The aim of this report is to provide a review the nascent academic literature addressing the intersection between business model thinking and cultural heritage. Special attention is devoted to such cases and perspectives that could offer some guidance and experience applicable to the eight rural and remote cultural heritage community areas that constitute the pilot cases of SECReTour. The findings will be used as a springboard to discuss how a business model perspective can contribute to a better understanding of cultural offerings (and vice versa). Likewise, the results can provide inspiration for how to attract tourist and other stakeholders to cultural heritage sites. The findings from the review will be supplemented with insights from the grey literature (white papers, reports etc.) and illustrative case examples.

Some of the key findings from the literature include the following:

- Research on cultural business models is dominated by case studies from the European continent, not least Italy.
- Cultural business models are linked to the geographical location as well as the meanings and feelings associated with them (authenticity, health, tradition etc.).
- Cultural business models often address challenges in the local community (e.g. youth unemployment, depopulation, low educational level etc.). Cultural offerings can be a vehicle for social value creation.
- The review highlights the importance of partnerships and multi-stakeholder collaboration. While individual entrepreneurs can play a pivotal role in pioneering cultural business models, the case studies also highlight the importance of local volunteers, public authorities, other cultural institutions etc.
- Research on cultural business models often draws on social entrepreneurship literature and place-based perspectives, although other theories and models have also enriched the conversations.
- The reviews call for more focus on new types of revenue channels, partnerships, governance mechanism, and contracts. Innovating cultural business models is key for strengthening communities, attracting tourists, and promoting economic development.
- The review suggests that additional attention needs to be paid to innovative ways of supporting local place-identity building and creating adequate place images among potential visitors on a limited budget, given the challenging operational conditions characterizing many remote and peripheral areas.

The review is one of the first attempts to take stock of the literature on cultural business models. Hopefully, the findings can draw attention to some of the dominant barriers and opportunities for maintaining and developing cultural business models. Moreover, we hope the review can be a source of inspiration for changemakers interested in developing new ways to create, deliver and capture value from cultural offerings. First of all, this applies to the eight pilot areas of the SECReTour project, but the

ambition is to develop practices and tools that can be transposed also to other remote and rural areas with valuable cultural heritage. Ultimately, this would contribute new perspectives and cases also to future academic work in this field.

This report is part of the SECReTour project funded by the European Commission.

1. Understanding Cultural Heritage from a Business Model Perspective

This report explores how business model thinking has been applied in the study of cultural heritage. A business model perspective can highlight gaps in current practices and identify opportunities for future improvements of cultural offerings.

1.1 Why Talk About Business Models?

Cultural heritage sites play an important role in our collective memory and can be part of the glue that bring communities together. Moreover, cultural heritage sites around the world are also a major business which attract millions of cultural tourists each year with major economic, social, and environmental impacts. However, there has been only limited research examining the underlying organisational architectures of cultural heritage sites and the multiple stakeholders surrounding these offerings.

The aim of this study is to explore how a business model perspective can add new insights into the inquiry of how cultural heritage sites create, deliver and capture value for stakeholders. A better understanding of the cultural business models can uncover gaps in the existing offerings and diffuse knowledge of good practice examples.

We examine this question by reviewing the nascent literature examining the interaction between business models and cultural heritage. Moreover, the review will supplement the findings with a number of short case examples, which illustrate a number of inspiring cultural business models.

We argue that business model thinking can help explaining current imbalances in cultural offerings. For instance, a business model perspective can be an inspiration for cultural heritage communities developing sustainable approaches to local development and cultural tourism. Cultural tourism can be defined as: "(...) a form of tourism in which cultural attractions are the main reason to visit a destination, offering the tourist an opportunity to understand and appreciate the essence of a place" (Amirato et al., 2022, p. 1943). It has been estimated that cultural tourism accounts for approximately 40 percent of global tourism (ibid).

1.2 Special Characteristics of Cultural Business Models

The business model literature got popularized in the 1990s as a new language for explaining the emergence of dotcom-businesses, which rapidly outperformed conventional 'bricks-and-mortar' businesses. However, business model thinking quickly became an integrated part of mainstream strategy and management thinking. For instance, the seminal book "Business Model Generation" by Alexander Osterwalder and Yves Pigneur (2010) also played an important role for the mainstreaming of business model thinking in theory and practice. Today, business model thinking is a well-established research field, which have been further subdivided into a number of sub-disciplines (Humblebæk & Pedersen, 2025).

Multiple definitions of business models exist (Humblebæk & Pedersen, 2025; Nikiel, 2019). At the broadest level, we define a business model as “(...) the firm’s value proposition and market segments, the structure of the value chain required for realizing the value proposition, the mechanisms of value capture that the firm deploys, and how these elements are linked together in an architecture” (Saebi et al., 2017, p. 567). Over the years, researchers have also developed various models and figures to visualize the building blocks of a business models. Figure 1 provides a summary of what we consider as the key components of a business model.

Figure 1: An overview of key business model building blocks. Source: Pedersen and Andersen (2023)

Cultural business models have a number of characteristics that set them apart from conventional business models. First, cultural business models are rooted in a specific location (place) which are associated with specific meanings, interpretations, feelings and history (sense of place) (Pedersen & Andersen, 2024). For instance, a study of the Swansea Bay City Region both emphasizes the natural resources as well as the unique local culture and community when discussing opportunities of local development and tourism” (Bowen et al., 2024). They are place-based rather than placeless. Second, cultural business models are complex by nature. Cultural business models combine economic and social logics. The governance is often characterized by network rather than hierarchy, where the maintenance and development of the cultural offerings are the responsibility of multiple stakeholders. Third, cultural business models are rooted in history rather than invented through entrepreneurial design. However, stakeholders can develop new offerings by tapping into the value embedded in existing cultural heritage sites, including walking paths, history tours, cultural events, accommodation, etc.

2. Methodology

The report is based on a review of the nascent scientific literature on cultural business models. In addition, we have supplemented the insights with case examples from relevant grey literature.

The literature review focused on articles on cultural business models and related terms. The search was conducted on two platforms, Scopus and Web of Science (WoS). The platforms were selected for the literature review due to their extensive coverage and academic rigor in the field (Albertsen, 2024).

Different search strings were explored to get a thorough overview of the literature on cultural business models. A search string is a combination of terms that encapsulate various aspects of what is being researched upon, i.e. alternative business models in cultural and heritage communities. The search string can be divided into separate thematic blocks which collect terms that describe the block and are similar, and to a certain extent, interchangeable, among each other.

In terms of language, the search was restricted to research results published in English. This is clearly a limitation of the overall scope and coverage given that a substantial amount of research pertaining to cultural business models and related issues is published in other languages than English, including other European languages. However, a substantial proportion of English-language publications nevertheless reports research that has been conducted in and/or targets countries beyond the English-speaking world. This ensures a relatively high degree of versatility in terms of perspectives and national/regional specifics. Conversely, using search terms only in one language ensures a higher degree of consistency and homogeneity in the outcome gained. In view of the high degree of diversity in the SECreTour team at large in terms of nationality and native languages, we are confident that the full academic scope of the project will be enhanced with key findings published also in other languages than English in the continued work.

The final search string evolved through a process of transformation. In total, 73 different search strings were tested to develop the final search string. The goal was to include as many relevant and interchangeable terms as possible within a block while avoiding overloading the thematic block. This ensures that combinations of search terms across blocks do not stray too far from the research question's focus. The final search string was as follows:

("business model*") AND ("case* stud*") AND (herit* OR cultur* OR local OR territor* OR rural OR "place based")*

An important restriction was to focus solely on publications drawing on one or more cases (Hoon, 2023). Moreover, we limited the search to final publications (i.e. not conference proceedings) that analysed cultural business models from a business and management perspective (see Table 1).

The final search string (4th of September 2024) yielded 171 results in Web of Science and 325 results in Scopus. When merged, through Mendeley, 110 duplicates were found and further excluded once. The final sum of results that emerged from the

above-mentioned search string is of 386. The search is filtered as follows in both platforms, and according to the platforms' respective filtering tools.

Filtering Criteria (<i>limited to</i>) by Platform							
Web of Science			Scopus				
Web of Science Categories	Document type	Language	Subject Area	Document type	Source type	Publication Stage	Language
Business, Management	Article, Early Access	English	Business, Management & Accounting	Article	Journal	Final	English

Table 1: Filtering Criteria (*limited to*) by Platform. Source: Authors' own elaboration

The results were documented in Excel, and key information from each article was recorded to facilitate the selection of relevant papers: authors; article title; publication year; source title; DOI, Abstract; keywords; and times cited. The authors then manually screened the abstracts of the articles for relevance. After closer examination, the large majority of articles did not address cultural business models directly. One research is that terms like “culture” are often used generically (e.g. when abstracts talk about creating a culture). In the end, the final list for review consists of 30 articles. Figure 2 depicts the number of paper citations among the articles included in this report.

Figure 2: Number of Paper Citations. Source: Authors' own Elaboration

The review inspired additional searches for more specific subthemes linked to cultural business models, including new forms of social contracting for cultural heritage (Humblebæk & Pedersen, 2025). This search combined academic articles and reports

from expert groups on the field. However, these results mainly served as inspiration and are not included in this report. Notably, this includes work within SECreTour itself and in INCULTUM, such as the pioneering work of the Granada pilot on creating and implementing alternative payment-for-service contracts. The reason is that these results (so far published primarily in project reports) are part of our own ongoing research efforts whereas the purpose of the literature was to widen the scope of existing state-of-the art literature against which these innovative efforts could be matched and further qualified. The final academic contributions of SECreTour will, of course, include a synthesis of previous work done by others and the innovations added by us. Yet at the present stage the former is dealt with separately to enhance transparency and clarity.

Moreover, additional searches were made through various organizational resources (government official websites, international organizations, such as UN databases or European-funded projects). A few examples of relevant resources are provided below:

Grey Literature References	
Database	Online Link
World Heritage Canopy (UNESCO)	https://whc.unesco.org/en/activities/?action=list&pattern=&canopy=1&order=dmd&submit=Search&index=21&maxrows=20
World Heritage and Best Practices World Heritage n°67 - April 2013 (UNESCO)	https://whc.unesco.org/en/review/67/
Cultural Heritage in Action, Creative Europe Programme (European Commission)	https://culturalheritageinaction.eu/case-studies/
Heritage Europa Nostra Awards, Creative Europe Programme (European Commission)	https://www.europeanheritageawards.eu/
Circular models Leveraging Investments in Cultural heritage adaptative reuse (CLIC Project, funded by the European Commission)	https://www.clicproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/D4.4-Case-Studies-of-Cultural-Heritage-Adaptive-Reuse-in-the-view-of-Circular-Economy.pdf

<p>Getting cultural heritage to work for Europe. Report of the Horizon 2020 Expert Group on Cultural Heritage. (European Commission)</p>	<p>https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/b01a0d0a-2a4f-4de0-88f7-85bf2dc6e004</p>
<p>Innovating Processes to Mitigate the New Emergencies: Proposal for a Collaborative Approach to Maintenance in the Archaeological Park of Pompei. Conference paper by Conservation of Architectural Heritage (CAH)</p>	<p>https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-33222-7_29</p>
<p>The Faro Convention (Council of Europe)</p>	<p>https://www.coe.int/en/web/culture-and-heritage/-/the-new-publication-the-faro-convention-at-work-in-europe-selected-examples-</p>
	<p>https://edoc.coe.int/en/cultural-heritage/10265-people-places-stories-faro-convention-inspired-experiences.html</p>

Table 2: Grey Literature References

3. Findings and Examples

Research on cultural business models is still at an embryonic stage. However, the review provides an overview of some of the common themes and issues addressed in the literature. The findings also highlight some of the barriers and success factors facing cultural business models.

The literature addressing the intersection between business models and cultural heritage is highly diverse, both in terms of aims, sector/geography, methodology, and theoretical perspective. Overall, the review clearly indicates that the literature on cultural business models is still at an embryotic stage. In the following sections, we will summarize some insights from the review supplemented with some illustrative case examples from the academic articles and the grey literature.

3.1 Geography of Cases

The cases are mostly found in a European context, with 8 of the 30 cases based in Italy (or at least one of them, in the case of multi-case studies). This aligns with existing research on cultural heritage, which highlights Italy's exceptionally high density of heritage sites, and the numerous initiatives developed around them nationally (Bertacchini et al., 2024; Zan et al., 2015). The map below represents the geographic location of the cases studies, and highlights some of the examples:

Figure 3: Geographic Location of Case Studies. Source: Authors' Own Elaboration

The case studies have different geographical characteristics. The studies focus both on *rural areas* (Fink et al., 2024; Cunha et al., 2020; Nguyen et al., 2018; Cantino et al., 2019; Bonini & Ferri, 2019; Sarkar & Sinha, 2015; Sudarmiadin et al., 2017; Di Gregorio, 2017; Charlebois & Mackay, 2010) as well as *urban areas* (Klein et al., 2021; Viviers & de Villiers, 2022; Poisson-de Haro & Normandin, 2020; Mioli et al., 2017; Cucari et al., 2020; Vrontis et al., 2021; Franzidis, 2019; Colovic & Schruoffenegger, 2021; Poisson-de Haro et al., 2020). Moreover, some cases are located in *natural reserves* (Amoamo et al., 2018; Scherrer, 2020; Cantino et al., 2017) whereas others focus on *industrial sites* (Szromek

et al., 2021) or *coastal areas* (ten Dam et al., 2023). Some case studies are geographically dispersed, depending on the nature of the organization. For instance, 4theRegion, a multistakeholder organization in the Swansea Bay City Region, brings together local businesses, community groups, local authorities, and farmers, among others, to support regional development (Bowen et al., 2024). As a result, the project's impact extends across urban, rural, and natural environments within the region. Conceptual papers that examine various case studies, for instance, to build a typology, are more difficult to classify according to the type of area (Hlady-Rispal & Blancheton, 2022; Ensign, 2023; Scuotto et al., 2023; Werthers et al., 2018; Dameri & Moggi, 2021; Dahles et al., 2020).

Overall, local geography plays a crucial role in shaping the case studies. As an example, agritourism is a business model capitalizing on the natural resources of Da Lat in Vietnam, which is well-known for its flower landscape (Nguyen et al., 2018, p. 4). However, the case studies are not only benefitting from the richness of resources in a given location. On the contrary, the business models can also be a way to tackle social and environmental challenges in a region (e.g. youth unemployment and low education levels) (Cucari et al., 2020; Franzidis, 2019). An example is the Foundation De Zilte Smaak, which focuses on developing saline agricultural products on the Dutch island of Terschelling (ten Dam et al., 2023). The initiative is directly influenced by the increasing soil salinization of coastal regions, a process accelerated by climate change, which was the driving force behind the founders' decision to experiment with saline agriculture.

Case Example: Geographic Embeddedness in Indigenous Entrepreneurship

Ensign (2023) examines how geographic embeddedness (remote, rural, or urban) shapes the opportunities and constraints faced by indigenous entrepreneurs, by arguing that business models are deeply connected to their location, taking a place-based approach to entrepreneurship. One of the cases highlighted in Ensign's paper is Hui Ku Maoli Ola, a native plant nursery on the island of Maui, Hawaii, operating in an urban context. The initiative aims at protecting and preserving the cultural and natural heritage of Native Hawaiians through the commercialization of endemic plants and their role in traditional practices. The traditional and ecological knowledge is leveraged in the modern commercial practices. Institutional support, such as the US Native American Programs Act (1974), is tied to its geographic context, reinforcing its business model. Additionally, its partnership with Home Depot provides market access, a scaling opportunity made possible by its urban setting.

Table 3: Geographical Embeddedness. Source: Ensign (2023)

3.2 Sectors and Industries

The literature addresses the intersection between the management and protection of local cultural heritage and sustainable tourism as a tool for socio economic development. For instance, one stream of literature addresses different aspects of agritourism and ecotourism, e.g. local farming, preservation of natural resources, indigenous cultures, and endangered species (Di Gregorio, 2017; Cunha et al., 2020; Nguyen et al.,

2018; Sudarmiatin et al., 2017; Amoamo et al., 2018; Scherrer, 2020; Cantino et al., 2017). Another group of literature looks more into the role of various cultural institutions, including museums, opera houses, circuses and festivals (Whertes et al., 2018; Poisson-de Haro & Normandin, 2020; Cucari et al., 2020; Bonini Baraldi & Ferri, 2019; Poisson-de Haro et al., 2022). Last, researchers have also analysed the development, restoration and repurposing of historical houses with cultural heritage value for private purposes (Viviers & de Villiers, 2022).

Overall, the literature is diverse which makes it difficult to identify a clear sectoral pattern. For instance, some studies examine specific categories of products (Cantino et al., 2019; Di Gregorio, 2017; Charlebois & Mackay, 2010) whereas others look into the tourism potentials for different types of cultural heritage (Szromek et al., 2021; Moioli et al., 2018; Dameri & Moggi, 2020; Bonini Baraldi & Ferri, 2019; Di Gregorio, 2017; Cucari et al., 2020). Moreover, some studies draw on multiple case studies that do not necessarily fall under one sector (e.g. Ensign, 2023; Scutto et al., 2023; Dahles et al., 2020).

Case Example: Ecomuseum of Salt and Sea of Cervia

The Ecomuseum of Salt and Sea was born in 2013 to preserve the beauty of natural and urban landscapes, local culture and memory of Cervia, in the northern Italian region of Emilia-Romagna. It brings together all the cultural and natural heritage of Cervia (salt works, city centre, pine trees, etc.).

The Ecomuseum, developed together with the local government of Cervia, and as a part of the European *Culturecovery* Project, has developed patrimonial and heritage walks, as well as landscapes and community maps, where the Ecomuseum Antennas are depicted. The work of the Ecomuseum is highly dependent on the work of local *facilitators*, which are citizens that contribute through their local knowledge and experiences.

Table 4: Ecomuseum of Salt and Sea. Source: *The Faro Convention at work in Europe: selected examples*

3.3 Stakeholder Orientation

The literature identifies a number of stakeholders relevant for the maintenance and development of cultural business models. A distinction can be made between internal or external stakeholders depending on their involvement in the governance of the cultural business model (if such an entity exists).

Internal stakeholders are directly engaged in the governance of the site, cultural heritage, etc. These stakeholders can for instance be organised under a foundation (e.g. ten Dam et al., 2023), a cooperative (e.g. Fink et al., 2024), a partnership (e.g. Cantino et al., 2019) or a private entity that produces (e.g. Di Gregorio, 2017). For instance, in the sector of agriculture and agritourism, actors along the value chain join a common governance body (ten Dam et al., 2023). Another case relevant for this study is the public private partnership (PPP) of Royal Villa and Park Monza (Moioli et al., 2018). The PPP includes the Ministry of Culture and Tourism, the Region of Lombardy, and the municipalities of Milan and Monza.

External stakeholders offer various forms of contributions to the cultural business models, such as institutional or financial assistance, legitimization, and distribution channels. For instance, partnerships with the pertinent public administration facilitate operations and ensures the development of activities. The case of the festival Santiago a Mil illustrates how partnerships with public sector actors can increase the scale and scope of the business model (Poisson-de Haro et al., 2022). Collaborations with schools enabled projects such as “Teatro en la Educación” (theater in education), implementing theatre activities into the school curriculum. Furthermore, close relationship to the government of Santiago enabled public funding and legitimization of the festival as Chile’s most recognized theatrical and cultural event (ibid). External stakeholders can also be beneficiaries of the cultural business models. As an example, local citizens benefit from the activities of Hotel con Corazón, a social enterprise in Granada, Nicaragua, that reinvest profits into educational initiatives for local communities (Franzidis, 2019).

Case Example: Ecomuseum in Lanckorona
<p>Lanckorona Ecomuseum is a networked and open museum that covers the entire space of four rural municipalities near Cracow – Lanckorona, Kalwaria Zebrzydowska, Stryszów, Mucharz. The main goal of the Ecomuseum is to create local spaces for tourism, recreation, leisure and, as a consequence of profits, cultural and social activation of municipalities’ residents. It is a network of organizations and private actors, so there is no one owner (however the main umbrella organization is Gościniec 4 Żywiołów). It is financed by the individual social and private actors which are participating in Lanckorona Ecomuseum.</p>

Table 5: Ecomuseum in Lanckorona. Source: CLIC Database

3.4 Theories and Models

The findings from the review indicate that scholars make reference to a variety of theories and models in the analysis of cultural business models. Examples include the resource-based view (RBV) (Bowen et al., 2024; Scuotto et al., 2023; Cucari et al., 2020), legitimacy theory (Viviers & de Villiers 2022), institutional theory (Scuotto et al., 2023), and the multi-level perspective (MLP) (Ten Dam et al., 2023). However, it is relevant to highlight three perspectives of relevance for the study: - social entrepreneurship, the place-based perspective, and business model theory.

The literature on *social entrepreneurship* emerges as a prominent perspective for analysing cultural business models. 13 of the 30 articles address some type of social enterprise that balances financial and social outcomes. being relatively undaunted by scarce assets in pursuing their social venture. Social entrepreneurship is an ambiguous concept but can in general be defined as: “a process that catalyzes social change and addresses important social needs in a way that is not dominated by direct financial benefits for the entrepreneurs” (Mair & Marti, 2006, p. 36). A core characteristic of social entrepreneurs is thus linked to their ability to balance the social mission with economic profit (Cucari et al., 2020; Colovic & Schruoffeneger, 2021). In the words of Scuotto et al. (2023, p. 234): “Social entrepreneurship involves the pursuit of both economic goals and social and environmental objectives (...)”. As an example, the case of

Blue Penguins Pukekura is based on a social enterprise model, which supports the Māori indigenous people and protects the Taiaroa Headland (Pukekura) and endangered species (Stewart Island shags, fur seals, sea lions and blue penguins) (Amoamo et al., 2018, p. 487). A few articles in the review also apply different sub-categories of entrepreneurship, including talks about “indigenous entrepreneurs” (Ensign, 2023), “sustainable entrepreneurs” (Bowen et al., 2024; Cunha et al., 2020), “cultural entrepreneurs” (Poisson-de Haro et al., 2022), and “life-style entrepreneurs” (Cunha et al., 2020).

Another common theoretical approach used in the literature on cultural business models is the *placed-based perspective* (Fink et al., 2024; Cantino et al., 2017; Ensign, 2023; Di Gregorio, 2017). The theory of place has a long history in social science and can both refer to a geographical location and the meanings and interpretations ascribed to it (Gieryn, 2000; Guthrey et al., 2014; Andersen & Pedersen, 2024). As an example, Di Gregorio (2015) uses a place-based perspective in an analysis of Italian slow food, agritourism and the ‘albergo diffuso’ model (integrated but geographically dispersed hotels). Essentially, cultural business models can be seen as place-based business architecture which uses *location-specific resources to create and capture value, thereby profiting from and contributing to a “sense of place”* (Di Gregorio, 2017, p. 115).

Business model theory is also addressed explicitly by several authors (e.g. Cucari et al., 2020; Poisson-de Haro et al., 2022). For instance, Franzidis (2019) who systematically applies a modified business model canvas in the analysis of a social tourism business in Granada, Nicaragua. Interestingly, however, the articles in the review often use of the extant literature on business models in a rather generic way. Some studies combine business model research with other theoretical perspectives (e.g. social entrepreneurship), whereas others primarily make generic references to business model concept when discussing the cases in question. Overall, the results indicate that business model thinking remains at the fringes of the discussions of how to strengthen cultural offerings and the communities, which they are part of.

Case Example: Women’s Resilience Weaving Museum

Dům pod Jasanem (The House under the Ash Tree) in Czech Republic, established in 2010 by a Public Association led by a craftswoman passionate about weaving, is a Museum of Weaving dedicated to preserving and promoting the traditional weaving craft of the local region near the Krkonoše Mountains, or the Giant Mountains. The museum not only serves as a cultural hub but also as an educational center offering certified weaving lessons, which provide a crafts qualification recognized by the National Ministry of Education. Through partnerships with local municipalities and other artisans, the museum has developed a range of programs that help unemployed individuals acquire craft skills, allowing them to create and market their woven products. The museum also highlights other traditional crafts, contributing to the preservation and awareness of the region’s cultural heritage.

Table 6: Women's Resilience Weaving Museum. Source: Open Heritage EU

3.5 Challenges and Opportunities

Cultural business models are often a response to a problem, challenge, or threat, that needs to be addressed. Examples of challenges include unemployment (Cucari et al., 2020), financial crises (Poisson-de Haro & Normandin, 2020), climate change (ten Dam et al., 2023), health problems (Colovic, & Schruoffenegger, 2021), and over-exploitation of natural resources (Cantino et al., 2017).

However, a recurring theme in the literature is the tendency of entrepreneurs to turn challenges into opportunities and catalyzing local development (Amoamo et al., 2018; Cantino et al., 2017; ten Dam et al., 2023; Di Gregorio, 2017; Cucari et al., 2020; Cantino et al., 2019; Scherrer, 2020). For instance, Dameri and Moggi (2020) define cultural heritage as a form of “cultural common” which do not have to become a ‘tragedy’:

“Several studies during the last 30 years have demonstrated how it is possible to transform the ‘tragedy’ into a ‘comedy’ by implementing commons exploitation models based on rich and complex interactions between human motivations, public and private rules, self-organizing mechanisms, and other relevant factors” (Dameri & Moggi, 2020, p. 5).

The literature has explored the challenge-opportunity dynamic in various contexts, from financial crisis responses—where MMFA and OdM, two cultural organizations in Montréal, leveraged financial crises to redefine their value propositions and operational models (Poisson-de Haro & Normandin, 2020)—to climate-driven adaptation, as seen in the development of saline agriculture in response to rising sea levels (ten Dam et al., 2023). The table below summarises some of the challenge-opportunity patterns from the literature:

Challenges and Opportunities for Cultural Business Models		
Challenge	Opportunity	Case Examples
Financial dependency	Income diversification	<p><i>Lifestyle</i> entrepreneurs in rural tourism in Alto Alentejo, Portugal have developed a diversified set of activities to tackle tourism seasonality, originally, their main source of income (Cunha et al., 2020). Some examples include “organic farming, diverse tourism activities (such as accommodation or equestrian tourism), or the trade of farm food products (olive oil or wine)” (ibid, p. 223).</p> <p>Spannocchia is a thriving agritourism estate in Tuscany that combines farming, hospitality, and education. It produces its own wine and olive oil, sells premium products made from the rare Cinta Senese pig, and offers tourism and learning experiences. Originally, the estate faced challenges such as seasonal use, the risk of being divided up, and financial instability. Over time, it transformed into a diverse and sustainable business with multiple revenue streams (Di Gregorio, 2017).</p>
Lack of product awareness	Transformation of the product or practices	Saline agricultural products struggle with low consumer awareness. The Foundation De Zilte Smaak, which researches

		<p>saline farming and its market potential in the Netherlands, promotes these products as “healthy and locally produced”, transforming the consumers’ perception of the products to boost demand and encourage consumption (ten Dam et al., 2023)</p> <p>Fontanafredda, an Italian winery in Piedmont, developed its organic wine, Vino Libero, and shifted towards sustainable practices following significant transformations in the company’s history, including a financial crisis that resulted in bankruptcy in the 1930s (Cantino et al., 2019).</p> <p>The Dambimangari Indigenous community on Australia’s Kimberley coast faced low initial demand for Indigenous tourism. To boost awareness, they partnered with non-Indigenous operators like expedition cruises and game fishing tours, offering Indigenous art sales and multi-day immersion experiences. This strategy reduced start-up costs and supported gradual growth toward full Indigenous ownership of the enterprise, while increasing customer demands for Indigenous tourism experiences (Scherrer, 2020, p. 676).</p>
High operational costs	Collaborative governance models to share costs	<p>BPP, the sustainable tourism enterprise in the Otago Peninsula, New Zealand, led by Māori people, reduced its operational costs by sharing infrastructure, management and marketing costs with the Royal Albatross Centre (Amoamo et al., 2018).</p> <p>Wandjina Tours, the Indigenous tourism enterprise in the Kimberley region of Australia, reduced its operational costs by sharing flight access, logistics, and provisioning expenses with Leveque Wilderness Fishing and Adventure Charters, minimizing the financial burden of operating in a remote location (Scherrer, 2020).</p>
Lack of skilled or culturally aware staff	Training of external volunteers	<p>BPP encountered the potential issue of lack of authenticity in its tours and overall storytelling as a result of employing non-Māori guides. Therefore, BPP engaged Korako Karetao Trust representatives to train staff on telling Māori stories in ways that align with tikanga (customary practices) (Amoamo et al., 2018).</p>
Top-down governance structure	Co-creative approach to governance	<p>The governance structure of 4theRegion, a Welsh organization with over 200 members spanning local businesses, policy-makers, NGOs, and schools, integrates local stakeholders to promote the development of the Swansea Bay City Region. This approach challenges “one-size-fits-all” local development models, advocating instead for a place-based strategy that leverages the region’s rich environmental resources for sustainable growth (Bowen et al., 2023).</p>
Regulatory constraints	Leveraging policy	<p>Due to restrictive land use policies in rural Italy that limit the transformation of large estates into entirely different activities, agritourism emerged as an innovative way to integrate tourism into existing agricultural operations. Spannocchia, an agritourism venture in Tuscany, was established by adhering to these land-use regulations and combining hospitality with sustainable farming practices (Di Gregorio, 2017, p. 121).</p>
Socioeconomic issues	Local development at the core	<p><i>La Paranza Cooperative</i> tackled youth unemployment in Naples by employing local youth as tour guides, and collaborating with youth-led enterprises, outsourcing services required by the Catacombs, such as maintenance and event management (Cucari et al., 2020).</p>

		<p><i>Alpha</i>, the pseudonym used by Colovic & Schruoffeneger (2021) to describe the social enterprise that tackles obesity in the Brazilian favelas, aims at reducing this health problem in the area by providing healthy and affordable meal options, while employing locals and overall, improving the image of the favelas.</p> <p>As previously mentioned, <i>Hotel con Corazón</i> was created to address challenges in local education, reinvesting its profits into educational initiatives (Franzidis, 2019).</p>
Growing at the cost of losing the ethos	Establishing limits to growth	<p>At its core, BPP is grounded in indigenous values, such as limiting growth, i.e. “tiaki”, to safeguard the natural reserve where it operates and the protected species that inhabit it. BPP’s “self-imposed capacity” to restrain economic growth is based on the notion that “the business model could collapse because the penguin population collapses” (Amoamo et al., 2018, p. 489).</p> <p>BPP’s model could serve as a best practice in contrast to the cases of Coop and Eataly, two globalized corporations focused on Italian gastronomy, which face “risks of trivializing authentic cultural resources” in their “process of achieving scale” (Di Gregorio, 2017, p. 120). Despite operating in different sectors, both cases highlight the importance of “the sense of place” (ibid) and the need to impose growth restraints to maintain authenticity.</p>

Table 7: Challenges and Opportunities for Cultural Business Models. Source: Authors' own Elaboration

<p>Case Example: Case Example: Torre Guaceto Marine Protected Area (MPA)</p>
<p>The Torre Guaceto Marine Protected Area (MPA) in Italy is a coastal reserve defined as a place-based enterprise (Cantino et al., 2017) due to its role in managing local natural resources through community engagement and adaptive governance. Established to protect marine biodiversity and prevent overfishing, the MPA initially faced strong resistance from local fishermen when fishing bans were imposed to restore the ecosystem. However, through collaboration with scientists and policymakers, they co-developed a sustainable fishing model that not only revived marine ecosystems but also ensured economic stability for the fishing community.</p> <p>By 2005, regulated fishing was reinstated, with fishermen actively engaged in monitoring and governance, strengthening their role in resource management. Institutional innovations, such as the BioFish label and the Community of Organic Producers and Fishermen, further reinforced sustainability. This case highlights how integrating stakeholders into governance can turn a challenge into an opportunity, fostering both environmental conservation and local economic resilience.</p>

Table 8: Torre Guaceto Marine Protected Area (MPA). Source: Cantino et al., 2017

3.6 Success Factors

A key success factor is linked to the cultural significance and resources available. A cultural business model makes the local culture and historical uniqueness of a place at the core of the value proposition (Di Gregorio, 2017; Cucari et al., 2020). However, not all cultural business models have access to the same cultural, human, or financial resources. For instance, a resource-rich region with strong communities and a unique culture is in a better position to develop cultural offerings and attract tourists than other places where this is not the case (Bowen, 2023, p. 10-11). As an example, the work of Cucari et al. (2020, p. 24) illustrates how the cultural value embedded in the Rione Sanità neighborhood created an opportunity for developing the historic sites and thereby creating value for tourists and the community alike. In many other areas, key preconditions for such a development are yet to be established (e.g. Ensign, 2023; Nguyen et al. 2018) which mirrors the 'below zero' scenario found also in some, while not all, the SECReTour pilots (a term rooted in INCULTUM work, cf. Smith & Block, 2024, p. 29, which we now intend to further qualify, inter alia, in view of the present review).

A key success factor is linked to the individual characteristics of the entrepreneurs, such as artistic and cultural motivations, entrepreneurial vision or personal legitimacy and financial resources from core actors to the businesses (Wrethes et al., 2018; Viviers & de Villiers, 2022). However, cultural business models are typically the result of a concerted effort with participation of multiple stakeholders. For instance, the literature highlights the role of volunteers, who is rooted in the local community (Scuotto et al., 2023; ten Dam et al., 2023; Bowen, 2023). To align the value proposition with local needs and resources, the literature also suggests the establishment of partnership structures and participatory governance, which take into account the voices of public, private, and community stakeholders. These governance structures have been defined as "collaborative" (Szromek et al., 2021), "participative" (Dameri & Moggi, 2020) or "community engagement" (Werthers et al., 2018). Strong local engagement fosters a sense of pride, benefiting business models, as locals become "*promoters and teachers of the values and methods of sustainable development in their local community and in their relationships with the tourists*" (Cantino et al., 2017, p. 519).

Partnerships can also create synergies which enable innovation of the cultural business models. As an example, the partnership between Montréal's cultural district, Quartier des Spectacles, and the light festival Montréal en Lumière (MEL) enabled the latter to develop its events in a recognized area of the city (Poisson-de Haro & Normandin, 2020). Partnering can potentially also reduce free-rider problems and opportunistic behaviour. For instance, aligning the interests of producers and sellers with contracts and a common governance structure can improve transparency, increase control and promote value co-creation among stakeholders (Di Gregorio, 2017; ten Dam et al., 2023). The latter aspect feeds essential experiences into ongoing work in SECReTour focusing on the creation of new types of payment-for-services contracts between local public and private stakeholders to ensure the daily management and maintenance of cultural heritage. That work takes further a successful implementation of such models in the context of INCULTUM relative to the maintenance of historical irrigation systems in Altiplano de Granada (cf. Humlebæk & Pedersen, 2025 Coppin & Guichard, 2025).

The exact design of the governance structure will depend on the cultural business model in question and the stakeholders involved. As an example, a foundation can be

established that bring the stakeholders together, organize joint activities, and communicate the cultural business model to the outside world (e.g. tourists). However, collaboration does not imply that everyone should have an equal say in the maintenance and development of a cultural business model. Without a governance structure and a backbone organisation, it will be difficult to coordinate existing activities and develop new ones (Szromek et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2018). The literature highlights the key role that local administrations play in overseeing the management of cultural heritage sites. As an example, the Marshal’s Office of the Silesian Voivodeship plays a key role in governing and coordinating the Industrial Monuments Route (establishing the route, overseeing its development, and promoting its sites) (Szromek et al., 2021).

Last, cultural business models are to a large extent made possible by the demands of external stakeholders (e.g. tourists). For instance, recurrent references are made to the increasing demands from customers on matters related to authenticity, sustainability, and healthy lifestyles (Cantino et al., 2019, p. 262; Papadopoulos et al., 2020). According to Cunha et al. (2020, p. 224), rural tourism entrepreneurs seem to “(...) be particularly well positioned to respond to the “new demand” made up of high potential market niches interested in unique local heritage experiences, authenticity and sustainability”. For instance, Poisson-de Haro and Normandin (2020) explain how the light festival Montréal en Lumière offered high-end cultural and gastronomic options, allowing it to differentiate themselves from competitors.

Case Example: Senia – Olive Tree Conservation and Routes

Taula del Sénia Commonwealth was created in 2006 “with a view to promoting extensive collaboration among municipalities and administrations, while also fostering cooperation with economic and social sectors. This partnership promoted the creation of the Sénia Territory Association, formed 50% by the Commonwealth and 50% by local economic sectors, which work together to promote the territory”, such as tree owners, oil producers, restaurants and tourism operators (Ministry of Culture, 2023).

The Oil and Ancient Olive Trees of Sénia project has established a network of millenary olive trees across three regions in the Northeastern coast of Spain - Valencia, Aragon and Catalonia-, dedicated to protecting the heritage of local communities and the landscapes these trees embody. It was a 4-year (2009 to 2013) joint-collaboration between the Taula del Sénia Commonwealth and the Sénia Territory Association. The project was the starting point for other related projects to support tourism, entrepreneurship and employment under the umbrella of the ‘Ancient Olive Trees of the Territorio Sénia’ initiative.

Table 9: Senia – Olive Tree Conservation and Routes. Source: Cultural Heritage in Action

Communication and knowledge sharing is also important for creating awareness about the cultural business model to tourists and other stakeholders (local governments, potential funders etc.). It can be done through social media, excursions, workshops and other events (food tasting, presence in festivals or fairs, etc.) (ten Dam et al., 2023). For instance, tourists visiting the Guido mine in Poland can try miners’

workwear and take part in mining activities (Szromek et al., 2021). Emphasis should be on two-way communication is important ensures, where the stakeholders involved in the cultural business model gain feedback from each other to ensure continuous development of the cultural offerings (ten Dam et al, 2023). A fundamental aspect of the cultural business model is the incorporation of local narratives into communication strategies. By connecting local challenges or the inherent characteristics of a product to its community, businesses ensure the transmission of a holistic understanding of cultural heritage (e.g. Vrontis et al., 2021; Amoamo et al., 2018; Poisson-de Haro et al., 2022).

Strengthening cultural business models also calls for adaptation and repurposing of existing cultural sites and spaces (Dameri & Moggi, 2020). For instance, an albergo diffuso model can transform declining villages into dispersed hotels without altering the original architectural and cultural fabric¹ (Di Gregorio, 2017). The development of the cultural business model may also involve developing new combinations of income from e.g. public grants, private fundraising, ticket sales, accommodation etc. (Cucari et al., 2020; Dameri & Moggi, 2020). Such strategy makes better use of the multiple resources available within a given place. As an example, Spannocchia successfully integrated agriculture, heritage preservation, and tourism, using visitor income to sustain organic farming and landscape conservation (Di Gregorio, 2017).

Case Example: Comuniterràe
<p>Comuniterràe, launched in 2017, is a cultural initiative to preserve the Middle Lands' heritage and drive sustainable development through an Ecomuseum. Spanning two valleys and ten Italian communities, it highlights a unique landscape rich in biodiversity and historical artifacts.</p> <p>The project began by creating Community Maps with contributions from 250 locals, capturing the traditions, crafts, and dialects that define each community. Activities like Comunitours (guided community walks) promote cultural pride and attract sustainable tourism. QR-coded plates on heritage sites offer visitors easy access to historical information.</p> <p>The project continued to grow through digital adaptations during COVID-19 and earned multiple awards, including the 2019 European Heritage Award. Comuniterràe stands as a model for participatory governance, strengthening community identity and supporting local development through cultural tourism.</p>

Table 10: Comuniterràe. Source: Cultural Heritage in Action

¹ [https://www.alberghidiffusi.it/the-albergo-diffuso-model/?lang=en#:~:text=It%20is%20defined%20as%20a,%E2%80%9D%20\(Dall'Ara\).](https://www.alberghidiffusi.it/the-albergo-diffuso-model/?lang=en#:~:text=It%20is%20defined%20as%20a,%E2%80%9D%20(Dall'Ara).)

4. Advancing Cultural Business Models in the Future

The review directed attention toward the multiple challenges and opportunities associated with cultural business models. These findings can also be used to identify future avenues for strengthening the value creating potentials of cultural business models, which will benefit communities, tourists and other stakeholders.

The findings outlined a number of different ways to organize, manage and develop cultural business models, that will create value for communities, tourists, and other stakeholders. Whatever the model, the success of cultural business models depends on the ability to balance economic and non-economic priorities to create attractive cultural offerings for tourists and strong local communities. In the following sections, we will shortly outline some future avenues for developing cultural business models.

4.1 New Types of Revenue Channels

Cultural business models are complex architectures with a multitude of loosely coupled stakeholder groups, who individually often do not have the incentives and resources to develop the collective cultural offerings. There is a need to explore opportunities for developing new mixes of revenues, that in combination advance the cultural business models. Public and private sources of income can for instance come from accommodation, education, local food, transportation, sport, conservation activities, monitoring, job training and employment services, arts and crafts, camping, cultural events, farm tours, homestay with locals, festivals, and workshops.

4.2 New Types of Partnerships

Cultural business models can be thought of as a patchwork of stakeholders, resources, and activities, which create unique cultural offerings. The open boundaries of cultural business models also provide opportunities for exploring new forms of partnerships, which can bring new energy to the cultural offerings and attract tourists. Partnerships can also bring new sources of revenue (see above) to the cultural business models – either directly through financial contributions or indirectly through joint funding applications. Examples of potential partners include public schools, local museums, private companies, sport associations, public authorities, music and art festivals, and other cultural institutions.

4.3 New Types of Governance Mechanisms

Innovation does not happen by itself. The development of new partnerships and sources of revenue require an element of collaboration, coordination, and control (i.e. organisation). However, some cultural business models are vulnerable because they are too fragmented and dependent on dedicated individuals. Therefore, there is a need for discovering governance mechanisms that balance multi-stakeholder

participation with the existence of a backbone organisation, that can be the joint hub for concerted efforts to advance the cultural business models.

4.4 New Types of Contracts

Local community stakeholders often make an important contribution to the maintenance of cultural heritage sites, but they are not necessarily rewarded for their efforts. The costs and benefits of complex, cultural business models are not always evenly distributed among stakeholders. For instance, the maintenance of cultural sites may be shared by many community members, whereas the benefits from e.g. tourism are concentrated among a few stakeholders. Therefore, there is a need for explore new forms of social contracting and impact bonds that create incentives for all stakeholders to contribute to cultural business models.

The INCULTUM and SECReTour partner in Granada, Spain, is currently developing and implementing payment-for-service contracts in the context of age-old irrigation and water management systems where visitors are given access on certain pathways along the canals against formal and symbolic recognition of the irrigators communities and the service they are providing as well as help with the maintenance. It thus serves as an example of the relative novelty of such types of innovative business models within rural environments managing cultural commons. The rather nascent literature on the field is justified by the lack of empirical examples that could inform best practices in organisational structures and strategies. It is the ambition of SECReTour to implement this type of contract in other contexts and include them in academic studies.

4.5 New types of communication tools and strategies

Given the often-limited resources available for more conventional communication and branding efforts in the target communities of interest, it is worth exploring alternative low-budget routes of place identity building and place-brand image development. Such needs and ways of accommodating them have already been explored for selected pilots in the INCULTUM project (Smith & Block, 2025; Smith Block) and that work will be taken further in SECReTour. The real-life cases, approaches, and challenges identified via the present literature review will offer a more versatile basis for doing so. This includes a wide array of examples where the potential of innovative user-involving digital solution and utilization of tangible bottom-up cues in the immediate semiotic landscape of potential visitors would seem to have been acknowledged, but not as yet exploited to the full.

Case Example: Public-Private Partnership in The Royal Villa and Park of Monza

The Royal Villa and Park of Monza, Italy, serves as a best-practice example of cultural heritage conservation through a Preventive and Planned Conservation (PPC) approach. This long-term strategy is based in a Public-Private Partnership (3Ps) model, distributing responsibilities among public authorities, private companies, technical professionals, and a supervisory committee. Under a 22-year concession model, Nuova Villa Reale Monza S.p.A. manages the restoration, conservation, and valorization of the site while remaining under public oversight. Key to the model's success is its emphasis on risk prevention, regular maintenance, and stakeholder engagement.

The model leverages digital tools to support conservation efforts. Geographic Information Systems (GIS), Building Information Modeling (BIM), and software like Planet and Manpro.net are essential for organizing, analyzing, and preparing long-term plans. The formalized 3Ps agreement mandates the use of these tools, along with regular reporting and a cultural agenda.

Table 11: The Royal Villa and Park of Monza. Source: Moiola et al., 2018

5. Concluding Remarks

The study provided a review of the nascent literature that address the intersection between business models and cultural heritage. So far, the literature on business models has aid only piecemeal attention to culture and the role of place. However, business model thinking can potentially provide valuable insights about the organisational architectures underpinning cultural heritage sites and the surrounding communities. Improving cultural offerings can attract tourists, secure funding from public and private sources, and ultimately build more resilient communities.

The study is based on a qualitative database analysis of scholarly journals supplemented with illustrative case examples of cultural business models from Europe and beyond. The review of the existing body of literature addressing cultural business models inspired the formulation of the initial recommendations for strengthening complex, place-based, cultural offerings listed above. These will be integrated with the findings and recommendations already generated in the INCULTUM project which are now being taken further in the SECReTour project with a specific focus on using innovative business models as a lever for cultural tourism development in rural and remote areas. The eight heritage communities selected as pilot cases for that work – combined with experience gained in INCULTUM and related work – offer a versatile basis for contributing new dimensions to the existing literature reviewed here as well as to producing tangible outcomes to the benefit of the communities themselves.

A limitation of the present study concerns the novelty of the field. The review revealed that not all studies explicitly adopt a business model perspective on cultural offerings. As the field of literature on cultural business models mature, it will be possible to make stronger conclusions about the topics addressed in the findings section. The review should thus be seen as a first attempt to identify tendencies and patterns in the literature on cultural business models. Moreover, it serves as a stepstone for the continued contribution to work along these lines within the SECReTour project, with a particular focus on empowering heritage communities in rural and remote areas.

5.1 Acknowledgements

This Report is part of the SECReTour project which have received funding from the European Commission.

6. References

Aas, C., Ladkin, A., & Fletcher, J. (2005). Stakeholder collaboration and heritage management. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 32(1), 28–48

Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)

Albertsen, R. R. (2024). Outcomes of Paradox Responses in Corporate Sustainability: A Qualitative Meta-Analysis. *Business & Society*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/00076503241255498>

Allan, C. & Curtis, A. (2005). Nipped in the bud: why regional scale adaptive management is not blooming. *Environmental Management*, 36(3), 414-425.

Altman, J. (2009). The hybrid economy and anthropological engagements with policy discourse: A brief reflection. *The Australian Journal of Anthropology*, 20(3), 318–329. doi:10.1111/j.1757-6547.2009.00039.x

Alvord, S. H., Brown, L. D., & Letts, C. W. (2004). Social Entrepreneurship and Societal Transformation: An Exploratory Study. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 40(3), 260-282. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021886304266847>

Amit, R., & Zott, C. (2010). Business Model Innovation: Creating Value in Times of Change. 5. <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1701660><https://ssrn.com/abstract=1701660>

Ammirato, S., Felicetti, A.M., Linzalone, R. & Carlucci, D. (2022). Digital business models in cultural tourism. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 28(8), 1940-1961. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEBr-01-2021-0070>

Amoamo, M., Ruckstuhl, K., & Ruwhiu, D. (2018). Balancing Indigenous Values Through Diverse Economies: A Case Study of Māori Ecotourism. *Tourism Planning and Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21568316.2018.1481452>

Andersen, K. R., & Pedersen, E. R. G. (2024). Place and sense of place in local manufacturing: How local fashion and textile companies in Norway work with and through place-based tensions. *Local Economy*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/02690942241306015>

Ateljevic, I., & Doorne, S. (2000). Staying within the fence: Lifestyle entrepreneurship in tourism. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 8(5), 378–392.

Baker, T. & Nelson, R.E. (2005). Creating something from nothing: resource construction through entrepreneurial bricolage. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 50(3), 329-366. Doi: 10. 2189/asqu.2005.50.3.329.

Bérard, L., & Marchenay, P. (2008). From localized products to geographical indications. *Awareness and Action, Bourg-en-Bresse: CNRS Ressources des terroirs*.

Bertacchini, E., Revelli, F., & Zotti, R. (2024). The economic impact of UNESCO World Heritage: Evidence from Italy. *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, 105, 103996-. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.regsciurbeco.2024.103996>

- Björklund, T.A. & Krueger, N.F. (2016). Generating resources through co-evolution of entrepreneurs and ecosystems. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, 10(4), 477-498. Doi: 10.1108/jec-10-2016-063
- Blay-Palmer, A. & Betsy Donald (2006). A Tale of Three Tomatoes: The New Food Economy in Toronto, Canada, *Economic Geography*, 82 (4), 383-399.
- Boluk, K. A., & Mottiar, Z. (2014). Motivations of social entrepreneurs: Blurring the social contribution and profits dichotomy. *Social Enterprise Journal*, 10(1), 53-68.
- Bonini Baraldi, S., & Ferri, P. (2019). From communism to market: business models and governance in heritage conservation in Poland. *Journal of Management and Governance*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10997-018-09448-8>
- Bosworth, G., & Farrell, H. (2011). Tourism entrepreneurs in Northumberland. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 38(4), 1474-1494.
- Bowen, R., Burvill, S., Cummings, B. & Themelidis, L. (2024). A new approach to entrepreneurship and regional development: key roles of purpose and well-being in the Swansea Bay City Region. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 30 (10), 2443-2462. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEER-03-2023-0320>
- Brauers, W.K.M. & Ginevicius, R. (2009). Robustness in regional development studies. The case of Lithuania. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 10 (2), 121-140. doi: 10.3846/1611-1699.2009.10.121-140
- Brest, P., & K. Born. 2014. Giving thoughts: Deconstructing impact investing. *Stanford Social Innovation Review*, http://tcblogs.org/public_html/wp-content/uploads/TCB_GT-VIN1-14.pdf?width=100
- Budyldina, N. (2018). Entrepreneurial universities and regional contribution. *International entrepreneurship and management journal*, 14(2), 265-277.
- Burns, P. (1999). Paradoxes in planning: Tourism elitism or brutality? *Annals of Tourism Research*, 26(2), 329-348. doi:10.1016/S0160-7383(98)00099-1
- Cantino, V., Devalle, A., Cortese, D., Ricciardi, F., & Longo, M. (2017). Place-based network organizations and embedded entrepreneurial learning: Emerging paths to sustainability. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEER-12-2015-0303>
- Cantino, V., Giacosa, E., & Cortese, D. (2019). A sustainable perspective in wine production for common-good management: The case of Fontanafredda biological “reserve.” *British Food Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-06-2018-0351>
- Cater, E. (2006). Ecotourism as a Western construct. *Journal of Ecotourism*, 5(1-2), 23-39. Doi:10.1080/14724040608668445
- Centobelli, P., Cerchione, R., & Esposito, E. (2019). Exploration and exploitation in the development of more entrepreneurial universities: a twisting learning path model of ambidexterity. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 141, 172-194.
- Charlebois, S., & Mackay, G. (2010). Marketing culture through locally-grown products: The case of the Fransaskoisie Terroir products. *Problems and Perspectives in*

Management. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84870283920&partnerID=40&md5=94ea6cad5cae099f5d770623f87d90eb>

CHCfE Consortium (2015). Cultural heritage counts for Europe. Full report, June, available at: [www. encatc.org/culturalheritagecountsforeurope/outcomes/](http://www.encatc.org/culturalheritagecountsforeurope/outcomes/)

Chen, H. & Rahman, I. (2018). Cultural tourism: an analysis of engagement, cultural contact, memorable tourism experience and destination loyalty. *Tourism Management Perspectives*, 26, 153-163.

Choi, N., & S. Majumdar (2014). Social Entrepreneurship as an Essentially Contested Concept: Opening a New Avenue for Systematic Future Research. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 29 (3). 363–76.

Coppin, F., & Guichard, V. (2025). Tourism as a tool for social and territorial cohesion: Exploring the innovative solutions developed by INCULTUM pilots. In *Innovative Cultural Tourism in European Peripheries* (pp. 7-27). Routledge.

CLIC Project. (2021). Deliverable 4.4: Case Studies of Cultural Heritage Adaptive Reuse in the View of Circular Economy. *European Commission*. Retrieved from <https://www.clicproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/D4.4-Case-Studies-of-Cultural-Heritage-Adaptive-Reuse-in-the-view-of-Circular-Economy.pdf>

Cohen, B. (2006). Sustainable valley entrepreneurial ecosystems. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 15(1), 1–14.

Colovic, A., & Schruoffeneger, M. (2021). Institutional Voids and Business Model Innovation: How Grassroots Social Businesses Advance Deprived Communities in Emerging Economies. *Management and Organization Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/mor.2020.66>

Croce, F. (2017). Contextualized indigenous entrepreneurial models: a systematic review of indigenous entrepreneurship literature. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 23(6), 886–906.

Council of Europe. (2022). The Faro Convention at work in Europe: Selected examples. Retrieved from <https://www.coe.int/en/web/culture-and-heritage/-/the-new-publication-the-faro-convention-at-work-in-europe-selected-examples->

Cucari, N., & K. Nuhu (2017). Co creation of Value in Relationship Crowdfunding Territory: An Exploratory Study in the Italian Context. *Proceedings of the 9th European Conference on Intellectual Capital*. *Intellectual Capital: Its Application in Practice*, 71–79.

Cucari, N., D'Angelo, E., Esposito, E., & Ciasullo, M. v. (2020). Assessing the Social Entrepreneurship Business Model: An Exploratory Case Study in the Italian Cultural Heritage Sector. *Entrepreneurship Research Journal*, 10(4). <https://doi.org/10.1515/erj-2019-0316>

Cultural Heritage in Action. (2021). Good practices. Retrieved from <https://culturalheritageinaction.eu/case-studies/>

Cunha, C., Kastenholz, E., & Carneiro, M. J. (2020). Entrepreneurs in rural tourism: Do lifestyle motivations contribute to management practices that enhance sustainable

entrepreneurial ecosystems? *Journal Of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 44, 215–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2020.06.007>

Dahles, H., Khieng, S., Verver, M., & Manders, I. (2020). Social entrepreneurship and tourism in Cambodia: advancing community engagement. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 28(6), 816–833. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2019.1706544>

Dameri, R. P., & Moggi, S. (2020). Emerging business models for the cultural commons. Empirical evidence from creative cultural firms. *Knowledge Management Research and Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14778238.2019.1664945>

Dell, K., Mika, J.P. & Warren, L. (2017). Indigenous entrepreneurial ecosystems: a New Zealand perspective. *Academy of Management Proceedings*, p.16725, Academy of Management, Briarcliff Manor, NY, <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMBPP.2017.16725abstract>.

Della Torre, S. (2003a). Piano di manutenzione e consuntivo scientifico nella legislazione sui lavori pubblici, in Della Torre, S. (Ed.), *La Conservazione Programmata Del Patrimonio Storico Architettonico*, Guerini e Associati, Milano, 25-29.

Della Torre, S. (2003b). La valutazione degli oneri economici nella conservazione programmata, in Della Torre, S. (Ed.), *La Conservazione Programmata Del Patrimonio Storico Architettonico*, Guerini e Associati, Milano, 133-145.

Della Torre, S. (2010). Preventiva, integrata, programmata: le logiche coevolutive della conservazione, *Pensare la prevenzione. Manufatti, usi, ambienti*, XXVI International Conference Scienza e Beni Culturali, Arcadia Ricerche, Venezia, Bressanone 13-16 luglio, 67-76.

Della Torre, S. (2014). Oltre il restauro, oltre la manutenzione, in Della Torre, S. (Ed.), *Proceedings of the International Conference Preventive and Planned Conservation Monza La strategia della Conservazione programmata, Dalla Progettazione Delle Attività Alla Valutazione Degli Impatti*, 7, Nardini Editore, Mantova and Firenze, 1-10.

Della Torre, S. & Moiola, R. (2012). Designing an active monitoring system: the planned conservation project in Monza and Brianza province, in Mendes Zancheti, S. and Similä, K. (Eds), *Measuring Heritage Conservation Performance, 6th Seminar on Urban Conservation – Measuring Heritage Conservation Performance*, CECI & ICCROM, Olinda and Roma, 142-147.

Di Domenico, M., Haugh, H. & Tracey, P. (2010). Social bricolage: theorizing social value creation in social enterprises. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 34 (4), 681-703.

Di Gregorio, D. (2017). Place-based business models for resilient local economies: Cases from Italian slow food, agritourism and the albergo diffuso. *Journal of Enterprising Communities*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-02-2015-0016>

Ensign, P. C. (2023). Contextual impact on indigenous entrepreneurs around the world: geographic location, socio-cultural context and economic structure. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship & Small Business*, 49(1). <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJESB.2023.131648>

- Esposito De Falco, S., T. Volpe, & N. Cucari. (2015). Civic Crowdfunding e Valore Del Territorio: Un'analisi Empirica Attraverso Due Piattaforme Italiane. *Economia e diritto del terziario*, 1, 185–202
- Etzkowitz, H., & Zhou, C. (2017). *The triple helix: university–industry–government innovation and entrepreneurship*. New York: routledge
- Europa Nostra. (2024). Heritage Europa Nostra Awards. Retrieved from <https://www.europeanheritageawards.eu/>
- European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. (2015). Getting cultural heritage to work for Europe: report of the Horizon 2020 expert group on cultural heritage. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/745666>
- Eyring, M., M.W. Johnson & N. Nair. (2011). New business models in emerging markets. *Harvard Business Review* January/February, 89–95
- Franzidis, A. (2019). An examination of a social tourism business in Granada, Nicaragua. *Tourism Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TR-04-2017-0076>
- Foss, N.J. & Saebi, T. (2017). Fifteen years of research on business model innovation: how far have we come, and where should we go? *Journal of Management*. 43(1), 200-227.
- Fudge, M., Ogier, E. & Alexander, K.A. (2021). Emerging functions of the wellbeing concept in regional development scholarship: a review. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 115, 143-150. Doi: 10.1016/j.envsci.2020.10.005
- Geels, F. W. (2002). Technological transitions as evolutionary reconfiguration processes: A multi-level perspective and a case-study. *Research Policy*, 31(8–9), 1257–1274. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(02\)00062-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(02)00062-8)
- Gibson-Graham, J. K. (2006). *A postcapitalist politics*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press
- Gieryn T.F. (2000) A space for place in sociology. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 26, 463–496
- Guerrero, M., Kirby, D., & Urbano, D. (2006). A literature review on entrepreneurial universities: an institutional approach. Anais da 3rd conference of pre-communications to congresses. Business economic department, autonomous university of Barcelona
- Guthey, G. T., Whiteman, G., & Elmes, M. (2014). Place and Sense of Place: Implications for Organizational Studies of Sustainability. *Journal of Management Inquiry*, 23(3), 254-265. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1056492613517511>
- Hanks, S. H., Watson, C. J., Jansen, E., & Chandler, G. N. (1994). Tightening the Life-Cycle Construct: A Taxonomic Study of Growth Stage Configurations in High-Technology Organizations. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 18(2), 5–29. <https://doi.org/10.1177/104225879401800201>
- Hardin, G. (1968). The tragedy of the commons. *Science*, 162 (1), 1243-1248

Hebb, T. (2013). Impact Investing and Responsible Investing: What Does it Mean? *Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment* 3 (2): 71–74.
doi:10.1080/20430795.2013.776255

Hess, C., & Ostrom, E. (2007). Understanding knowledge as a commons: From theory to practice. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press

Hoon, C. (2013). Meta-Synthesis of Qualitative Case Studies: An Approach to Theory Building. *Organizational Research Methods*, 16(4), 522-556.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428113484969>

Hlady-Rispal, M. & Blancheton, B. (2022). The diamond model: A French luxury cluster model embedded in regional heritage, *Journal of Small Business Management*, 60(2), 420-446. Doi: 10.1080/00472778.2020.1716588

Humblebæk, C.J. & Pedersen, E.R.G. (2025). Innovative business models for cultural tourism: Advancing development in peripheral locations. 54-67 in Borowiecki, K.J., Fresa, A., & Civantos, J.M.M. (Eds.). *Innovative Cultural Tourism in European Peripheries*. Routledge

Isenberg, D.J. (2011). The entrepreneurship ecosystem strategy as a new paradigm for economic policy: principles for cultivating entrepreneurship. Institute of International European Affairs, Dublin, Ireland, May 12

Jones, C., S. Svejnova, J. Strandgaard Pedersen & B. Townley. (2016). Misfits, mavericks and mainstreams: Drivers of innovation in the creative industries. *Organization Studies Special Issue*, 37(6), 751–68.

Kavaratzis, M. (2005). Place branding: a review of trends and conceptual models. *The Marketing Review*, Vol. 5 No. 4, pp. 329-342

Kirkwood, J. & Walton, S. (2010). What motivates ecopreneurs to start businesses? *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*, 16(3), 204-228

Klein, S. B., de Vasconcelos, M., Lima, R. D. C., & Dufloth, S. C. (2021). Contributions From Entrepreneurial Universities to The Regional Innovation Ecosystem of Boston. *Revista Gestao & Tecnologia-Journal of Management and Technology*, 21(1), 245–268. <https://doi.org/10.20397/2177-6652/2021.V21i1.2021>

Korsgaard, S., Müller, S. & Welter, F. (2021). It's right nearby: how entrepreneurs use spatial bricolage to overcome resource constraints. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 33 (1-2), 147-173. Doi: 10.1080/08985626.2020.1855479

Koslosky, M. A. N., de Moura Speroni, r., & Gauthier, O. (2015). Ecosistemas de inovação: uma revisão sistemática da literatura. (ano 2015). *Revista espacios*, 36(03).

Kronenberg, M. (2007). Turystyka dziedzictwa przemysłowego–próba sprecyzowania terminologii. Dziedzictwo przemysłowe jako strategia rozwoju innowacyjnej gospodarki, 33–42.

Kwong, C., Tasavori, M. & Wun-mei Cheung, C. (2017). Bricolage, collaboration and mission drift in social enterprises. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 29 (7-8), 609-638. Doi: 10.1080/08985626.2017.1328904

Lachmann, L.M. (1970). The Legacy of Max Weber. *Glendessary*, Berkley, CA.

- Lampel, J., Lant, T., & Shamsie, J. (2000). Balancing Act: Learning from Organizing Practices in Cultural Industries. *Organization Science* (Providence, R.I.), 11(3), 263–269. <https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.11.3.263.12503>
- Lang, R., Fink, M., & Kibler, E. (2014). Understanding place-based entrepreneurship in rural Central Europe: A comparative institutional analysis. *International small business journal*, 32(2), 204–227. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0266242613488614>
- Lechner, C., Delanoë-Gueguen, S. & Gueguen, G. (2022). Entrepreneurial ecosystems and actor legitimacy. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*, 28(9), 466–491. Doi: 10.1108/ijeb-03-2020-0165
- Lester, D. L., Parnell, J. A., & Carraher, S. (2003). Organizational Life Cycle: A Five-Stage Empirical Scale. *The International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 11(4), 339–354. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb028979>
- Levi-Strauss, C. (1967). *The Savage Mind*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago
- Lounsbury, M., J. Gehman & M.A. Glynn (2019). Beyond homo entrepreneurus: Judgment and the theory of cultural entrepreneurship. *Journal of Management Studies* 56, 1214–36
- Luporini, A., & Parigi, B. (1996). Multi-Task Sharecropping Contracts: The Italian Mezzadria. *Economica (London)*, 63(251), 445–457. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2555016>
- Mair, J., & Marti, I. (2009). Entrepreneurship in and around institutional voids: A case study from Bangladesh. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 24(5), 419–435.
- Mair, J., & Marti, I. (2006). Social Entrepreneurship Research: A Source of Explanation, Prediction, and Delight. *Journal of World Business* 41 (1), 36–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2005.09.002>
- Martin, L. (2016). Public Procurement Practice. Public-Private Partnership (P3): Facilities and Infrastructure. Guidance. *National Institute of Governmental Purchasing to state and local government procurement officials*, pp. 1-14, available at: www.ncppp.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/02/Public-Private-Partnership-P3-Facilities-and.pd_.pdf
- Mathie, A., & Cunningham, G. (2003). From clients to citizens: Asset-based Community Development as a strategy for community-driven development. *Development in Practice*, 13(5), 474–486. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0961452032000125857>
- McGee, J. E., Peterson, M., Mueller, S. L., & Sequeira, J. M. (2009). Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy: Refining the Measure. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 33(4), 965–988. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6520.2009.00304.x>
- McGehee, N. G., & Kim, K. (2004). Motivation for agri-tourism entrepreneurship. *Journal of Travel Research*, 43, 161–170
- McKeever, E., Jack, S., & Anderson, A. (2015). Embedded entrepreneurship in the creative re-construction of place. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 30(1), 50–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2014.07.002>
- Mik-Meyer, N. (2020). Multimethod Qualitative Research. In D. Silverman (Ed.), *Qualitative Research*, 5, 357–374. SAGE Publications

- Mika, J.P., Felzensztein, C., Tretiakov, A. & Macpherson, W.G. (2022). Indigenous entrepreneurial ecosystems: a comparison of Mapuche entrepreneurship in Chile and Māori entrepreneurship in Aotearoa New Zealand. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 1–19, <https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2022.15>
- Miller, D., & P. Friesen. (1980). Archetypes of organizational transition. *Administrative Science Quarterly* 25(2), 268–99
- Miller, D., & P. Friesen. (1983). Successful and unsuccessful phases of the corporate life cycle. *Organization Studies* 4(4), 339–56
- Miller, D., & P. Friesen. (1984). A longitudinal study of the corporate life cycle. *Management Science*, 30(10), 1161–83
- Ministry of Culture (2023). Green Book of Cultural Heritage. <https://www.cultura.gob.es/libro-verde-patrimonio/en/buenas-practicas-todas/taulasenia.html>
- Mintzberg, H. (1984). Power and organization life cycles. *Academy of Management review*, 9(2), 207-224
- Moioli, R., Boniotti, C., Konsta, A., & Pili, A. (2018). Complex properties management: Preventive and planned conservation applied to the Royal Villa and Park in Monza. *Journal of Cultural Heritage Management and Sustainable Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCHMSD-06-2017-0035>
- Neumeyer, X., & Santos, S. C. (2018). Sustainable business models, venture typologies, and entrepreneurial ecosystems: A social network perspective. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 172, 4565–4579
- Nguyen, N. T. H., Suwanno, S., Thongma, W., & Visuthismajarn, P. (2018). The attitudes of residents towards agro-tourism impacts and its effects on participation in agro-tourism development: The case study of Vietnam. *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*, 7(4)
- North, D. C. (1990). *Institutions, Institutional Change and Economic Performance* (1st ed.). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511808678>
- Ormiston, J., K. Charlton, M. S. Donald, & R. G. Seymour (2015). Overcoming the Challenges of Impact Investing: Insights from Leading Investors. *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship* 6 (3). 1–27. doi:10.1080/19420676.2015.1049285
- Osborne, S. (2010). *The new public governance: Emerging perspectives on the theory and practice of public governance*. London: *Routledge*
- Osterwalder, A., & Pigneur, Y. (2010). *Business model generation: A handbook for visionaries, game changers, and challengers*. John Wiley & Sons
- Ostrom, E. (1990). *Governing the commons: The evolution of institutions for collective action*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ostrom, E. (2015), *Governing the Commons*, Cambridge University Press, New York, NY
- Otgaar, A. (2010). Industrial tourism: Where the public meets the private (No. EPS-2010- 219-ORG)

- Pacifico, M. G. (2024). Innovating Processes to Mitigate the New Emergencies: Proposal for a Collaborative Approach to Maintenance in the Archaeological Park of Pompei. In M. L. Germanà, N. Akagawa, A. Versaci, & N. Cavalagli (Eds.), *Conservation of Architectural Heritage (CAH)* (pp. 353–362). Springer International Publishing
- Panyik, E., Costa, C., & Rátz, T. (2011). Implementing integrated rural tourism: An event-based approach. *Tourism Management*, 32(6), 1352–1363. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2011.01.009>
- Pedersen, E.R.G. & Andersen, K.A. (2023). Greenwashing from a Business Model Perspective. *Journal of Business Models*, 11, (2), 11-24
- Pierre, J. (2000). *Debating governance*. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Poisson-de Haro, S., & D. Montpetit. (2012). Surviving in times of turmoil: Adaptation of the Theatre Les Deux Mondes business model. *International Journal of Arts Management* 14(3), 16–31
- Poisson-De Haro, S., Espejo, A., & Martí, I. (2022). Business Model Evolution and Entrepreneurial Adaptation of Festivals: The Case of Santiago a Mil. *International Journal of Arts Management*. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85131533066&partnerID=40&md5=f781de5792d2aa92e60a32b4cf13ecab>
- Poisson-de Haro, S., & Normandin, F. (2020). Transitions in the Life Cycle of Cultural Organizations. The Cases of Four Montreal-Based Organizations. *International Journal of Arts Management*. Volume 22, Number 3, 17–33
- Porter, M. (1985). *Competitive advantage: Creating and sustaining superior performance*. Free Press
- Qastharin, A. R. (2016). Business Model Canvas for Social Enterprise. *Journal of Business and Economics* 7 (4): 627–37
- Ramkissoon, H., Weiler, B. & Smith, L.D.G. (2012). Place attachment and pro-environmental behaviour in national parks: the development of a conceptual framework, *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 20(2), 257-276
- REACH Project. (2018). Open-Heritage.eu: the online space of the REACH Social Platform. Retrieved from <https://www.open-heritage.eu/>
- Rhodes, R. A. W. (1996). The new governance: Governing without government. *Political Studies*, 44(4), 652–667
- Rhodes, R. A. W. (2007). Understanding governance: 10 years on. *Organization Studies*, 28(8), 1243–1264
- Roundy, P.T.; Bradshaw, M. & Brockman, B.K. (2018). The emergence of entrepreneurial ecosystems: a complex adaptive systems approach'. *Journal of Business Research*, 86, 1–10
- Saebi, T., Lien, L., & Foss, N.J. (2017). What Drives Business Model Adaptation? The Impact of Opportunities, Threats and Strategic Orientation. *Long Range Planning*. 50 (5), 567-581, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2016.06.006>

Sarkar, R., & Sinha, A. (2015). The village as a social entrepreneur: Balancing conservation and livelihoods. *Tourism Management Perspectives*.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2015.07.006>

Scherrer, P. (2020). Tourism to serve culture: the evolution of an Aboriginal tourism business model in Australia. *Tourism Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TR-09-2019-0364>

Scuotto, A., Cicellin, M., & Consiglio, S. (2023). Social bricolage and business model innovation: a framework for social entrepreneurship organizations. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSBED-02-2022-0094>

Scheyvens, R. (1999). Ecotourism and the empowerment of local communities. *Tourism Management (1982)*, 20(2), 245–249. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177\(98\)00069-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177(98)00069-7)

Sheldon, P. J., Daniele, R., & Sheldon, P. J. (2017). Social Entrepreneurship and Tourism: Philosophy and Practice (1st ed.). *Springer International Publishing AG*.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-46518-0>

Shrivastava, P. & Kennelly, J.J. (2013). Sustainability and place-based enterprise. *Organization and Environment*, 26 (1), 83-101

Sims, R. (2009). Food, place and authenticity: local food and the sustainable tourism experience. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 17 (3)

Smith, V., & Block, M. (2025). Place branding from scratch: Naming, framing, and finding Campina de Faro. In *Innovative Cultural Tourism in European Peripheries* (pp. 28-53). Routledge.

Smith, V., Block, M. & Carpentari (in submission). In the beginning was the name: The role of naming and framing in creating sustainable tourism in peripheral areas. *Target journal: European Journal of Tourism Research*.

Stevenson, H. H.; Roberts, M. J.; Grousbeck, H. I., & Liles, P. R. (1985). *New business ventures and the entrepreneur* (2. ed.). R.D. Irwin

Suchman, M. C. (1995). Managing Legitimacy: Strategic and Institutional Approaches. *The Academy of Management Review*, 20 (3), 571–610. doi:10.2307/258788

Sudarmiatin, S., Handayati, P., Soetjipto, B. E., Hidayat, R., & Bukhori, I. (2017). Rural tourism management: Gap between expected and reality. *International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research*, 15, 279–289

Svejenova, S., M. Planellas, & L. Vives. (2010). An individual business model in the making: A chef's quest for creative freedom. *Long Range Planning* 43(2/3), 408–30

Szromek, A. R., Herman, K., & Naramski, M. (2021). Sustainable development of industrial heritage tourism – a case study of the Industrial Monuments Route in Poland. *Tourism Management*, 83, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2020.104252>

ten Dam, R., Vellinga, P. & Negacz, K. (2023). From experiment to market development: A case study of prospects and value chain of saline agriculture in Terschelling, the Netherlands, *NJAS: Impact in Agricultural and Life Sciences*, 95(1), 2211541, Doi: 10.1080/27685241.2023.2211541

The Patrimoni project, Council of Europe. (2021). People, Places, Stories - Faro Convention inspired experiences. Retrieved from <https://edoc.coe.int/en/cultural-heritage/10265-people-places-stories-faro-convention-inspired-experiences.html>

Theodoraki, C., Messeghem, K., & Rice, M. P. (2018). A social capital approach to the development of sustainable entrepreneurial ecosystems: An explorative study. *Small Business Economics*, 51(1), 153–170

Thompson, J.D. (1967), *Organizations in Action: Social Science Bases of Administrative Theory*, Transaction Publishers

Tödting, F. & Trippel, M. (2005). One size fits all? towards a differentiated regional innovation policy approach. *Research Policy*, 34 (8), 1203-1219. Doi: 10.1016/j.respol.2005.01.018

Torres Valdés, R. M., Lorenzo Álvarez, C., Castro Spila, J., & Santa Soriano, A. (2018). Relational university, learning and entrepreneurship ecosystems for sustainable tourism. *Journal of Science and Technology Policy Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSTPM-03-2018-0032>

Trubek, A. B. (2008). *Taste of place: a cultural journey into terroir* (1st ed., 20). University of California Press

Tushman, M. L., & C. A. O'Reilly, III. (1996). Ambidextrous Organizations: Managing Evolutionary and Revolutionary Change. *California Management Review*, 38 (4), 8–29

UNESCO World Heritage Centre. (2013). World Heritage and Best Practices: World Heritage n°67. Retrieved from <https://whc.unesco.org/en/review/67/>

Viviers, S. & de Villiers, J. (2022) Impact investments that have stood the test of time: Historical Homes of South Africa (1966-2020). *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 12(4), 1009-1026, Doi: 10.1080/20430795.2021.1891780

Vrontis, D., Basile, G., Tani, M., & Thrassou, A. (2021). Culinary attributes and technological utilization as drivers of place authenticity and branding: the case of Vascitour, Naples. *Journal of Place Management and Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPMD-03-2020-0024>

Werthes, D., Mauer, R., & Brettel, M. (2018). Understanding challenges and entrepreneurial self-efficacy during venture creation for entrepreneurs in cultural and creative industries. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 33(2), 265-288. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJESB.2018.090139>

Williams, D. R., Patterson, M. E., Roggenbuck, J. W., & Watson, A. E. (1992). Beyond the commodity metaphor: Examining emotional and symbolic attachment to place. *Leisure Sciences*, 14(1), 29–46. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01490409209513155>

Wyborn, C. (2015). Co-productive governance: a relational framework for adaptive governance. *Global Environmental Change*, 30, 56-67

Yunus, M., Moingeon, B., & Lehmann-Ortega, L. (2010). Building Social Business Models: Lessons from the Grameen Experience. *Long Range Planning*, 43(2), 308–325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2009.12.005>

Zahra, S.A., Gedajlovich, E., Neubaum, D.O. & Shulman, J.M. (2009). A typology of social entrepreneurs: motives, search processes and ethical challenges. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 25, 519-532

Zan, L., Bonini Baraldi, S., Lusiani, M., Shoup, D., Ferri, P., & Onofri, F. (2015). Managing cultural heritage. An international research perspective. Farnham: Ashgate

7. Appendix: Summary of Articles from Review

Article Title	Case country	Case Type	Methods	Case description	Theory	Authors	Journal
How production cooperatives operating a sharing economy business model innovate in rural places	Greece	In-depth single case study along seven years of field-work	Abductive approach. Qualitative multi-method approach (Mik-Meyer, 2020): “triangulation of the observation, interview, and document data” (ibid, p. 1218)	SteviaCo (a pseudonym) is a CSE-BM (Cooperatives with a Sharing Economy Business Model) located in Central Greece, which produces stevia as well as “processes the harvested crops and markets the final products with the idea of covering the whole value chain to generate better income for the farmers involved” (p. 1219). The authors ask <i>How can CSE- BMs foster innovations in structurally weak rural places?</i> (ibid) and define “SE- BMs as a collaborative production model that enables organizations to pursue innovation on a local level and focuses on the sharing of physical resources and knowledge” (ibid, p. 1223). And they argue that “the strength of CSE- BMs in developing process, service, product, and social innovation lies in their ability to reconfigure shared resources across communities and actors located on different levels of power and with different access to resources” (ibid, p. 1213). They also emphasize the tensions created across actors in the reconfiguration of shared resources and argue that a cooperative-like organization has the potential to turn that tension into innovation.	Place-based; social capital perspective; SE-BMs & social innovation; multi-level network model of regional innovation	Fink, M; Maresch, D; Lang, RC; Richter, R; Chatzihristos, G	R & D MANAGEMENT Journal

<p>The diamond model: A French luxury cluster model embedded in regional heritage</p>	<p>Nouvelle-Aquitaine, France</p>	<p>Comparative in-depth case studies for two years</p>	<p>Abductive approach. Semi-structured interviews, non-participant observation, and archival documents (p. 428).</p>	<p>The authors seek to explain “<i>What kind of value creation process takes place in luxury clusters and how does it potentially influence the competitiveness of the regional economic actors?</i>” (p. 421) by looking at “two institutional clusters in the brandy and leather luxury sectors in Nouvelle-Aquitaine, France”. In “gathering economic actors’ perceptions of the benefits they capture”, they create a diamond model, inspired by BMs representations (p. 428). The authors find that the value creation process in luxury clusters is highly influenced by the interplay of economic, societal, and environmental value flows. Specifically, they highlight how these flows are anchored in local expertise and heritage, particularly through the involvement of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) that preserve and transmit unique craftsmanship. The study shows that luxury clusters rely on specialized know-how and regional resources, including institutional connections, to generate and sustain competitiveness.</p>	<p>No clear theoretical framework.</p> <p>Uses concepts of business model representations (Amit & Zott, 2001, 2015; ensiy-Rispal & Servantie, 2018; Oskametal., 2018); value creation, value flow, luxury networks and clusters;</p>	<p>Hlady-Rispal, M; Blanchet on, B</p>	<p>JOURNAL OF SMALL BUSINESS MANAGEMENT</p>
<p>Contextual impact on indigenous entrepreneurs around the world: geographic location, socio-cultural</p>	<p>12 countries</p>	<p>Stratified non-random sampling to select</p>	<p>Qualitative methods: storytelling, testimonials gathered through interviews</p>	<p>The author investigates how geographic location, socio-cultural context and economic structure foster or hinder entrepreneurship among indigenous peoples (p. 151). The sample of a variety of businesses, representing remote, rural and urban contexts spreads globally. The author aims at stepping away from a Eurocentric and top-down approach to the research and therefore emphasizes the</p>	<p>Indigenous entrepreneurial ecosystem theory and socio-cultural embeddedness (Dell et al.,</p>	<p>Ensign, P. C.</p>	<p>INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP & SMALL BUSINESS</p>

context and economic structure		examples globally. In total, there are over 50 businesses included in the sample.	and observations, archival accounts.	<p>relevance of expressing the “viewpoints of indigenous persons themselves” (p. 152).</p> <p>Across the three elements defined in the RQ, several findings are highlighted. The effect of geographical location on entrepreneurship depends on whether it is rural, remote or urban. For instance, remote locations increase traditional practices, fostering entrepreneurship, but may hinder it due to financial and geographical isolation. In the case of urban entrepreneurs, they usually adopt hybrid models, which often lead to innovation and broader connectivity. Socio-cultural context usually provides legitimacy to entrepreneurship, although often it is a source of internal conflict. Lastly, targeted government and community support for indigenous entrepreneurship lead to business thriving. Nonetheless, exploitative structures that limit land rights or financial resources significantly affect indigenous entrepreneurship. Concluding, the article highlights indigenous entrepreneurship as a source for community empowerment and resilience through cultural revitalization and socio-economic development.</p>	2017; Roundy et al. 2018; Mika et al. 2022) and place-based indigenous entrepreneurship (Croce, 2017).		
CONTRIBUTIONS FROM ENTREPRENEURIAL UNIVERSITIES TO THE REGIONAL INNOVATION	Boston, United States	Multiple case study	“Semi-structured interviews, document analysis and	Universities have been studied as organizations promoting not only education but social and economic development, an approach coined by the term “entrepreneurial university” (Etzkowitz & Zhou, 2017; Centobelli et al., 2019). Within this field, the authors investigate <i>how do entrepreneurial universities contribute to Boston's innovation ecosystem?</i> (p. 248) Institutions like Harvard and MIT	<i>No clear theoretical framework.</i> Uses the concepts of innovation ecosystem (Koslosky &	Klein, SB; de Vasconcelos, MCLR; Lima, RDC; Dufloth, SC	REVISTA GESTAO & TECNOLOGIA-JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT AND TECHNOLOGY

ECOSYSTEM OF BOSTON			observa- tion" (p. 246).	<p>play a pivotal role in fostering Boston's entrepreneurial environment by leveraging the innovation ecosystem and applying the principles of the entrepreneurial university. These contributions are organized around six key dimensions.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resources: public and private funding, as well as alumni endowments. Universities also have their own funds to channel investments. 2. Infrastructure: including cutting-edge interdisciplinary research facilities such as innovation labs. 3. Teaching: entrepreneurial thinking in the curricula. 4. Networking: initiatives such as visiting committees, to connect academia with industry leaders 5. Entrepreneurial centers: incubators for student startups 6. Ecosystem actors and context: striking number of competent, future entrepreneurs and governmental and industry partnerships 	Gauthier, 2015); entrepreneurial university (Budyldina, 2018; Guerrero et al., 2006);		
A new approach to entrepreneurship and regional	Wales, Swansea Bay	Single case study	Multi-source and multi-phased	"4theRegion, founded in 2019, is an organisation with over 200 members that includes local businesses (large and small), community groups, charities, universities and colleges, local authorities, policymakers and all relevant stakeholders aimed at	Resource-based view (RBV), particularly resource	Bowen, R; Burvill, S; Cummings, B;	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENTREPRENEURIAL

<p>development: key roles of purpose and well-being in the Swansea Bay City Region</p>	<p>City Region</p>		<p>qualitative research: semi-structured interviews, document analysis</p>	<p>promoting local development within the Swansea Bay City Region area. The ethos of the organization is centered on asset-based local development, underpinned by a social purpose and well-being, driven in part by the Well-being of Future Generations Act in Wales” (p. 5). The authors use this case study to provide insights into the growing body of literature investigating the role of well-being and purpose in regional development (p. 2). Four recurrent themes are identified, which represent the role of the Region in rural development: people, place process and purpose. These are “closely aligned with the Well-being of Future Generations Act in Wales” (p. 13).</p> <p>The organization serves as a forum where partnerships with local actors are created to foster conversations and activities (such as conferences) with other stakeholders in order to tackle local issues, which the authors define under the code of <i>people</i> as an “ecosystem with multi-stakeholder involvement” and aim at “mapping who is doing what in the region” (p. 8).</p> <p>The theme <i>place</i> tackles both challenges and opportunities of the region in adapting to well-being and rural development, such as the lack of funding and job opportunities, and the culturally and environmentally rich nature of the region.</p> <p>The theme <i>process</i> related to the ongoing nature of regional development, highlighting a</p>	<p>bricolage, derived from Levi-Strauss (1967) (p. 4). (e.g. Baker and Nelson, 2005)</p> <p>Contribution to literature in well-being and regional development, purpose and well-being (Brauers and Ginevicius, 2009; Fudge et al., 2021). Place-based development (Tödting and Trippel, 2005).</p>	<p>Themelidis, L</p>	<p>BEHAVIOR & RESEARCH</p>
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				<p>progressive shift in paradigm and a focus on community-based asset development. A top-down and one-size-fits-all traditional approach on rural development is identified as a challenge, and a bottom-up and a 'community-based asset approach' is identified as a rather progressive way to tackle local issues.</p> <p>The theme <i>purpose</i> has a "purpose-driven and place-based social purpose" (p. 12), where actors identify the relevance of, for example, empowering future generations through volunteering and engaging them in the local culture.</p>			
<p>Entrepreneurs in rural tourism: Do lifestyle motivations contribute to management practices that enhance sustainable entrepreneurial ecosystems?</p>	<p>Southern Portugal (Alto Alentejo)</p>	<p>Empirical study based on eight case studies</p>	<p>Qualitative research based on in-depth semi-structured interviews, on-site observation for 3 months</p>	<p>This study investigates the role of lifestyle entrepreneurs in rural tourism in the Portuguese region of Alto Alentejo. The underlying motivations of these tourism agents are passion for rural traditions and sustainability. The study collects stories from eight entrepreneurs that have their own small tourism accommodation units. According to the results, there are two distinguished groups: the more lifestyle-oriented entrepreneurs who prioritize sustainability and community development and the less lifestyle-oriented ones that emphasize family heritage and financial stability. The first group leans towards local networks, focuses on organic farming and has a more holistic view of sustainable tourism. Some challenges are addressed such as seasonality. In order to tackle such shortage of visitants, the entrepreneurs rely on a diversified set of activities that allows them to reduce financial instability. The study finds that the more</p>	<p>Sustainable entrepreneurial ecosystems (. Cohen, 2006; Neumeyer & Santos, 2018; Theodoraki et al., 2018; Torres Valdés, 2018) & lifestyle entrepreneurs (Ateljevic & Doorne, 2000; Bosworth & Farrell, 2011; Marcketti,</p>	<p>Cunha, C; Kastenholz, E; Carneiro, MJ</p>	<p>JOURNAL OF HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM MANAGEMENT</p>

				life-style oriented entrepreneurs generally contribute more greatly to a sustainable entrepreneurship ecosystem of their region, by incorporating sustainability practices and self-development motivations in their businesses, such as cross-selling, investing in organic agriculture and a round ecological business management.	Niehm, & Furloria, 2006).		
From experiment to market development: A case study of prospects and value chain of saline agriculture in Terschelling, the Netherlands	Terschelling, Netherlands	Empirical case study	Participatory observation and semi-structured interviews. Value mapping from three months of observations	<p>The case study is based on the foundation “De Zilte Smaak”, working in the research and development of saline agriculture and the viability of saline agricultural products into the Dutch market. The foundation is established in the island of Terschelling, in the Netherlands, and comprises the work of local citizens and tourism entrepreneurs. The present study investigates “<i>what are the prospects for the development of the value chain for saline agricultural products on Terschelling?</i>” (p. 3). The authors map the value chain of saline agricultural products, and they use the MLP framework to understand the transition from traditional freshwater agriculture to saline water in three levels, which emphasize the geographical characteristics of the case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Landscape level. Increasing trend towards healthier local foods. - Socio-technical regime. Interdependencies among actors for innovation in the field. Policies constraining traditional agriculture may foster saline agriculture 	Multi-level perspective (MLP); value chain	ten Dam R.; Vellinga P.; Negacz K.	NJAS: Impact in Agricultural and Life Sciences

				<p>- Socio-technical niches. Due to the climate vulnerabilities of islands, Terschelling is viewed as a favourable location for the development of sustainable innovations.</p> <p>The value chain mapping provides examples of challenges at different stages. For instance, at the production level, a “chicken and egg” problem is found, due to the lack of demand for saline agricultural products which would justify farmers’ investments, but the lack of supply is hindering the creation of a reliable market. In the marketing and retail stage, although this market remains a niche and its escalation to a national mass market is perceived as challenging due to the lack of awareness and remoteness of the island, the market has potential for tourism offers in the island.</p> <p>The authors conclude on the positive prospects for the development of saline agriculture in the island while they highlight the need to tackle challenges such as product awareness and labour intensiveness.</p>			
Social bricolage and business model innovation: a framework for social	South of Italy	Multiple comparative case studies. 15	Selection of relevant SEOs in managing cultural sites through some sort	In the sector of cultural heritage management, social entrepreneurship organizations (SEOs) that operate within resource-constrained environments can adopt a “social bricolage” approach and adapt their business models to “respond to unsatisfied social needs and to optimize resources” (p. 235).	Social bricolage (e.g. Di Domenico, 2010; Zahra et al., 2009). (Social) business model	Scuotto A.; Cicellin M.; Consiglio S.	Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development

<p>entrepreneurship organizations</p>		<p>SEOs analysed (Social Entrepreneurship Organizations)</p>	<p>of alternative business model focused on public use out of a larger database of SEOs in Southern Italy in the third sector. Data collection was based on documentary analysis (e.g. “organizational charts, annual reports, partnership documentation, budgets,</p>	<p>The paper draws from 15 case studies of SEOs operating in the Southern Italian third sector across various industries, to answer the RQ: “How do SEOs modify their business model to develop social innovation?” (p. 236). These SEOs mainly worked for the “recovery and enhancement of the artistic and the cultural heritage” (p. 259).</p> <p>The case studies reveal that SEOs in the cultural heritage sector implement nine key business model innovation strategies: co-participation, generative leadership, socially oriented activities, asset-based community development, cross-subsidization, surplus management, grassroots involvement, social relationships, and empowerment. Collaboration with local communities is key to create social value. One example from the case #3, an association managing churches, illustrates how the SEO was highly reliant on the contributions from local experts to develop its business plan or how the case #15, an association working with churches and historical buildings created job opportunities for local volunteers. Other cases emphasize how the SEOs reinvested in social programs for the local communities (e.g. educational and cultural initiatives).</p>	<p>innovation (e.g. Yunus et al. 2010; Foss & Saebi, 2017).</p> <p>Asset-based community development (e.g. (Mathie & Cunningham, 2003)</p>		
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			business plan, social responsibility statements”, p. 243) and semi-structured interviews.	Drawing from the results, the authors draw a conceptual model to depict that the “innovation cultural SEOs implement in their business model goes towards a social business model innovation (Spiess-Knafl et al., 2015) in which social bricolage intrinsically takes place” (see p. 258). They find that “investment in the entrepreneurial process of cultural heritage has social returns that strongly contribute to economic growth and the creation of new jobs” (p. 259). Despite the scarcity of resources for SEOs, SEOs “become “community enterprises” strongly rooted in their local area and focused on a cohesive economy” (p. 260).			
Impact investments that have stood the test of time: Historical Homes of South Africa (1966-2020)	South Africa	Abductive approach: document analysis and semi-structured personal interviews	Single case study	<p>Historical Homes of South Africa Limited established in 1966 aims at “buying, restoring and renting” (p. 1009) South African homes with a cultural heritage value. The company was established by Dr Anthony Rupert, a renowned philanthropist businessman in the country. The figure of the founder is key for this study, since the authors investigate how the company has remained successful overtime, by paying special attention to the image of Dr Rupert in shaping the company’s thriving.</p> <p>Drawing from legitimacy theory and defining the company as an impact-first impact investment, which prioritizes the social outcome of the business activity over financial returns, the authors find</p>	Legitimacy theory (Suchman, 1995); (impact-first) impact investment (Hebb 2013; Brest and Born 2014; Ormiston et al. 2015)	Viviers S.; de Villiers J.	Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment

				<p>that the company's legitimacy stems from various sources.</p> <p>The personal legitimacy of the founder allowed him to raise start-up capital and structure his initiative as a company rather than a charity, which the paper argues, provided the company with structural and procedural legitimacy to survive over time. Additionally, the company's periodic collaborations with social actors and public authorities in restoration projects and disaster relief efforts have contributed to its linkage legitimacy.</p> <p>The company maintains efficiency and financial viability through an in-house team of skilled craftsmen, which ensures internal and technical legitimacy. Overall, its focus on pragmatic and moral legitimacy stems from addressing both its own needs and those of its stakeholders, such as local tourism actors (p. 1021).</p> <p>The findings highlight how impact-first impact investors can endure over time by leveraging different sources of legitimacy tailored to their specific contexts and objectives.</p>			
Sustainable development of industrial heritage	Industrial Monument	Literature review,	Multiple case studies from the 42	The Industrial Monuments Route (IMR) in Poland is the largest (post-) industrial route consisting of 42 diverse sites that aims at preserving industrial heritage of and make it available to tourists. By doing	<i>No clear theoretical framework.</i> Uses	Szromek A.R.; Herman K.;	Tourism Management

tourism – A case study of the Industrial Monuments Route in Poland	Route, Southern Poland	interviews, document analysis and observations	sites that are part of the industrial monument route	so, the IMR contributes greatly, through its steady increase in popularity, to the socioeconomic development of the region (p. 2). Some of the most relevant site include the GUIDO Historic Coal Mine, breweries, and the Central Museum of Firefighting. A key initiative that showcases the increase in popularity is the Industriada, an annual festival centred around industrial tourism, where various events such as tours, concerts and workshops, inviting curious tourists to get to know the cultural heritage of the region. The authors investigate how can the sites be categorised based on their business model and the nature of the site itself. The four types found are the Post-Production Tourist Organizations (PPTO), Production and Tourist Enterprises (PTE), and Tourist Thematic Organizations (TTO). The analysis of these types suggests that the life cycle of these organizations presents two stages that may overlap or follow successively. These are the production and the tourism stage. The findings suggest that the PPTOs are the most common models and, along with PTEs, provide more authentic experiences by blending the history of (post)industrial sites with cultural heritage tourism. This combination presents a sustainable opportunity to 'remake' these locations, therefore, suggesting an innovative approach to sustainability and tourism.	concepts of (post-)industrial cultural tourism (Kronenberg, 2007; Otgaar, 2011) and business models (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010), taking a life-cycle of the organization approach (Lester et al., 2003; Mintzberg, 1984; Hanks et al., 1994).	Naramski M.	
Understanding challenges and	Not specified.	Qualitative	"Multiple case study	Entrepreneurial self-efficacy (ESE), characteristic of entrepreneurs in cultural and creative industries (CCI), is key in understanding their venture	Process literature on	Werthes D.; Mauer	International Journal of

<p>entrepreneurial self-efficacy during venture creation for entrepreneurs in cultural and creative industries</p>	<p>Likely Germany (authors).</p>	<p>research : observations; background data from the entrepreneurs (secondary data); discussion of analysis with entrepreneurs (data triangulation through phone</p>	<p>approach with replication logic” (p. 271). Sample: ten entrepreneurs in venture creation that all are part of a program “that aims at supporting them to ‘get their business on the road”” (ibid).</p>	<p>creation process, as it affects their entrepreneurial behaviour across various stages of this process. The article investigates “How does entrepreneurial self-efficacy influence entrepreneurial behavior?” and “How do entrepreneurs deal with entrepreneurial challenges?” and defines four phases in the venture creation process: searching, planning, marshalling, and implementing (Stevenson et al., 1985; McGee et al., 2009)</p> <p>The level of ESE varies across these stages: while during initial phases of searching ESE remains high, it decreases along the process. Difficulties related to identifying a value proposition hinder ESE levels during the planning phase, and lack of productivity and reach to customers is linked with the low levels of ESE observed during the marshalling phase, which is defined as the stage where resources are accumulated for the initiation of the business. Lastly, during the implementing phase, those entrepreneurs with low ESE levels experience difficulties in growing their businesses and setting clear provisions for the future of their initiatives.</p> <p>According to the analysis, there is a lack of ESE levels across the stages, which directly impacts entrepreneurial behaviour for CCI</p>	<p>entrepreneurship (Stevenson et al., 1985 McGee et al., 2009); CCI entrepreneurship (Lampel et al, 2000); planned behaviour and self-efficacy (Ajzen, 1991)</p>	<p>R.; Brettel M.</p>	<p>Entrepreneurship and Small Business</p>
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		calls and emails)		entrepreneurs. Therefore, the authors suggest the implementation of “support programs in which the entrepreneurs receive training on specific tasks, such as business practices” (p. 283), and refer to similar practices developed in the field of social entrepreneurship. The study also suggests the increase of entrepreneurial teaching in educational settings.			
Transitions in the life cycle of cultural organizations: The cases of four Montreal-based organizations	Montreal, Canada	“Case studies of four iconic Montreal-based cultural organizations” (p. 18).	Qualitative study. Longitudinal approach to track main changes in the organizations’ key transitions. Semi-structured interviews, document analysis. When available,	<p>Cultural organizations may adapt their business models at different stages, following certain transitions. This study investigates, by taking a life-cycle approach of the organization, how four salient cultural organizations in Montreal - Montréal en Lumière (MEL), Cirque Éloize (CE), Montreal Museum of Fine Arts (MMoFA), and Opéra de Montréal (OdM) – have developed their business models from birth to growth, growth to maturity and maturity to revival.</p> <p>The findings suggest that during the first stage, organizations focus in strengthening their customer value proposition and formalizing key resources and activities to support their initial growth. For instance, MEL created a distinct value proposition by providing unique gastronomic experiences with performing arts and light installations, and integrated their festival management through Équipe Spectra, ensuring coherence in their operations. CE partnered with Cirque du Soleil, therefore ensuring a strong legitimacy.</p>	Organizational life-cycle theory (Miller and Friesen, 1983, 1984); Business model canvas (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010).	Poisson-de Haro, S.; Normandin, F.	International Journal of Arts Management

			<p>quantitative data was reviewed: annual reports, strategic plans ...</p>	<p>From the growth to maturity stage, MEL reinforced its identity by moving its main event to Quartier des Spectacles, Montréal's cultural district. CE on the other hand gained independence from its previous partners and developed shows in other types of institutions, fostering its innovation.</p> <p>Lastly, from the maturity to revival stage, MMFA introduced bold exhibitions such as those on Disney or Jean Paul Gaultier to enlarge its customers' segments. It also engaged in international collaborations to increase its visibility and financial sustainability. OdM developed innovative performances such as those in metro stations and education kits for schools. The company also partnered with other opera houses to co-create and diversify its cost structure. These initiatives tackled challenges such as declining audiences, financial instability or increased competition.</p> <p>These findings highlight the importance of adapting business models during life-cycle transitions to ensure sustainability and resilience in the cultural sector.</p>			
Complex properties	Monza, Italy	Single case study	Qualitative study.	The Royal Villa and Park of Monza, Italy is of great cultural heritage relevance, and it is part of the Monza and Brianza Cultural District (MBCD)	Preventive and Planned Conservation	Moioli R.; Boniotti C.;	Journal of Cultural Heritage Management

<p>management: Preventive and planned conservation applied to the Royal Villa and Park in Monza</p>			<p>Secondary data evaluation from public documents on records, data base of the site, as well as rehabilitation and maintenance or organic programmes. Primary data collected from interviews, observations and a photographic survey.</p>	<p>project. In conserving its infrastructure, a Preventive and Planned Conservation approach was put in place. Responsibilities were distributed across a Public -Private Partnership (3Ps). The engaged authorities included public actors from the Consortium of the Royal Villa and Park of Monza and Infrastructure Lombarde S.pA (contracting authority), as well as private actors, such as the concessionaire Nuova Villa Reale Monza S.p.A, technical and professional staff and a supervisory committee.</p> <p>The authors investigate this integrated management model as an industry best-practice with regards to cultural heritage conservation. The plan is a concession model that enables the restoration, management and valorisation of the site to Nuova Villa Reale Monza S.p.A. under public supervision. The plan is supposed to last for 22 years.</p> <p>The PPC approach is based on long-term planning. In order to achieve this, the plan has developed various practices:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conservation plan, acting as a framework, including a technical handbook (architectural plans); a conservation programme (e.g. maintenance and risk prevention); long- 	<p>(PPC) (Della Torre, 1999, 2003a; Kerr, 2013); public-private partnership (3Ps) and concepts of “design-build-finance-operate-maintain” instrument of 3Ps (Martin, 2016), and cultural heritage as a factor for territorial capital, stemming from upstream perspective theories (CHCfE Consortium, 2015, pp. 195, 196, 197). The findings investigate</p>	<p>Konsta A.; Pili A.</p>	<p>and Sustainable Development</p>
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				<p>term economic budget; user handbook (non-technical involved stakeholders).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrated Information Systems, such as the Geographic Information Systems and Building Information Modeling, or Planet and Manpro.net software, key in organising and analysing conservation activities data and allowed for preparing and integrating long-term plans. - Formalised 3Ps Model through an agreement with distribution of responsibilities in clauses for mandatory use of the above-mentioned information systems, as well as regular reporting on conservation efforts. - Preventive conservation strategy, which included a risk assessment on potential environmental and structural risks and scheduled maintenance, aiming at preventing future more costly interventions. - Integrating the valorisation of the site by planning a cultural agenda. - Training and engagement of local stakeholders, by creating partnerships and ensuring long-term management through a bottom-up approach. <p>The 3Ps agreement proposes a positive model of “governance based on cultural/ scientific contents and on a rigorous control of the respect of the</p>	evidence-based policies.		
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				<p>agreement conditions” (p. 141). The article concludes with remarks on the need of investigating the economic viability of the model post-intervention, by tracking “number of visitors, ticketing, quality and quantity of users, number of cultural projects, number of partners” (ibid). The authors also highlight the relevance of management tools along the processes since this is expected to last over two decades. Lastly, the PPC model tackles a general challenge in the management of built cultural heritage (BCH) sector, such as short-term planning and lack of multi-disciplinary experts.</p>			
<p>The attitudes of residents towards agro-tourism impacts and its effects on participation in agro-tourism development: The case study of Vietnam.</p>	<p>Vietnam</p>	<p>Single case study on the Thai Phien Village, Da Lat City, Lam Dong Province,</p>	<p>Quantitative analysis. Statistical analysis and questionnaire. Correlation on participation in agro-tourism development and impact on</p>	<p>The development of agro-tourism activities in the town of Thai Phien in Central Vietnam, such as “the Flower Festival [...] farm tours for visitors to learn and do farming work, hands-on planting and picking of flowers, vegetables, and fruits in orchards or overnight at homestay with locals or at camping sites in the village to experience rural life” (p. 5) have implications on the socio economic development of the village. The research investigates attitudes of the locals towards such programmes and their correlation to demographic factors, as well as their participation in such activities.</p> <p>The attitudes found are classified as positive and negative across four areas of agro-tourism effects:</p>	<p><i>No clear framework.</i> The paper suggests previous studies in the field of rural development and agro-tourism.</p>	<p>Nguyen N.T.H.; Suwannos S.; Thongma W.; Visuthis majarn P.</p>	<p>African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure</p>

		Vi- etnam .	socioeco- nomic factors	<p>economic impacts, environmental impacts, socio-cultural impacts, and community involvement. The findings suggest that attitudes are generally positive, especially as “agro-tourism has contributed significant changes to their (the residents’) living such as diversification of local economic activities, and stimulation in tourism-related business opportunities. Furthermore, their quality of life has changed compared to before that due to agro-tourism provides more recreational opportunities and a variety of farming activities. It fully capitalizes on the local community resources and enhancement of their pride in the local community culture. The study has emphasized not only the impetus of cultural exchange and meet new people but also the education and share the farming techniques between locals and visitors. Additionally, the awareness of both the authorities and the community of the contribution of agro-tourism in the conservation of natural environment has enhanced more than prior. The infrastructure improvement such as road, sanitation, parking plot; and the landscape of this area” (p. 14).</p> <p>The findings also suggest that residents pay special attention to the economic and socio-cultural effects of agro-tourism. A key correlation was found between those residents who participated in agro-tourism activities (or community involvement) and economic and socio-cultural impacts. This result aligns with an overall finding, pointing</p>			
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				<p>to the positive relationship between positive attitudes to the impact of agro-tourism activities and participation in those activities.</p> <p>In light of the findings, the authors suggest further implementation in agro-tourism business courses to raise awareness on the benefits of these activities, increase the usage of media and communication and leverage the annual flower festival as well as fostering partnerships between locals and tourism providers.</p>			
<p>Assessing the Social Entrepreneurship Business Model: An Exploratory Case Study in the Italian Cultural Heritage Sector</p>	<p>Naples, Italy</p>	<p>Single exploratory case study.</p>	<p>Abductive approach method. Qualitative enquiry approach. Personal semi-structured interviews. Triangulation through analysis of secondary data (publicly</p>	<p>La Paranza Cooperative is a social enterprise (SE) in Naples that seeks to reduce youth unemployment in the Rione Sanità neighbourhood by revitalizing and leveraging local cultural heritage sites, such as the Catacombs of San Gennaro and San Gaudioso, for tourism.</p> <p>The paper investigates “How do social entrepreneurs design their business models in order to create both social and economic value?” (p. 3). It examines the cooperative’s business model, highlighting its success through direct and indirect contributions to the local economy.</p> <p>Central to the cooperative's business model is its value proposition, which delivers tailored benefits to diverse stakeholders: unique touristic</p>	<p>Social entrepreneurship: antecedents' framework, (Hossain et al., 2017) and ambidexterity (Tushman & O'Reilly 1996).</p> <p>RBV in SE (Choi & Majumdar, 2014).</p>	<p>Cucari N.; D'Angelo E.; Esposito E.; Ciasullo M.V.</p>	<p>Entrepreneurship Research Journal</p>

			<p>available documents).</p> <p>experiences for visitors, pride and belonging for locals, economic and social returns for sponsors, neighbourhood revitalization, and training and employment opportunities for youth.</p> <p>The authors measure the cooperative's impact using three KPIs: visitor numbers, square meters of recovered heritage, and jobs created (p. 17). Direct achievements include reopening historic sites, training youth as tour guides, installing LED lighting, and creating the "Holy Mile" itinerary, with visitor numbers growing from 6,308 in 2006 to over 129,830 in 2018. Indirect benefits include revitalized businesses, increased community pride, and enhanced visibility of the district through partnerships and fundraising efforts.</p> <p>Using Hossain et al. (2017) as a framework, the study identifies key characteristics of La Paranza's SE model: <i>innovativeness</i> in revitalizing the district, <i>proactiveness</i> in adapting the business model, and <i>risk-taking</i> in managing non-owned resources. The cooperative exemplifies social innovation by fostering community participation and cohesion, and network embeddedness through partnerships that <i>provide financial and organizational support</i>. Its sustainability orientation integrates environmental measures, economic self-reliance, and social commitments, transforming</p>	<p>Business model canvas (Qastharin, 2016).</p> <p>Focus on territory improvement through SE.</p>		
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				<p>challenges like bureaucracy and unemployment into opportunities for growth.</p> <p>The authors emphasize the centrality of <i>territory</i> in SE models, noting that the cooperative leverages undervalued heritage and local social challenges to create a "new equilibrium" (p. 24). This model identifies unfair marginalization, redefines value propositions, and fosters systemic change to uplift communities, positioning La Paranza as a benchmark for sustainable social enterprise development.</p>			
<p>Emerging business models for the cultural commons. Empirical evidence from creative cultural firms</p>	<p>Cases across Europe: Italy, Slovenia, Germany, Poland, Hungary, Croatia</p>	<p>Multiple-case study. "Nine cases have been selected as European best practice from the</p>	<p>Qualitative explorative study. Inductive approach. Data collection was based on participant observation, semi-structured interviews and</p>	<p>The tragedy of the commons (Ostrom, 1990), and more precisely, the tragedy of the cultural commons (Aas et al., 2005), has been at the core of European projects aiming at the development of innovative governance and business solutions for the sustainable preservation, valorization, and adaptive reuse of underutilized or neglected cultural heritage sites, fostering participatory approaches and public-private partnerships to address challenges of both overuse and underuse. The authors select nine cases from the project Forget Heritage and develop an archetype "BM canvas of successful addressing disuse-based tragedy of cultural commons" (p. 9), in order to answer their RQ: "how could CCFs manage the tragedy of the cultural commons?" (p. 2).</p>	<p>BMC (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010); governance of the commons (Ostrom, 1990); Tragedy of cultural commons and cultural heritage threats: overuse and underuse (Hess & Ostrom,</p>	<p>Dameri R.P.; Moggi S.</p>	<p>Knowledge Management Research and Practice</p>

		<p>Cultural Creative Firms (CCFs) involved in the three-year European project “Forget Heritage” (p. 2).</p>	<p>document analysis (reviewer internal reports and publicly available documents from the project).</p>	<p>Key results stem from “the importance of the local community’s commitment to participative governance, the sharing of knowledge that enhances an inter-organisational community of learning and the need for value co-creation to steer the CCF’s self-sustainability” (p. 2). In terms of project governance, the authors highlight “PPP [models] and participative governance systems” as best practices.</p> <p>Within the BM proposed, relevant aspects are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The value proposition must include a bottom-up approach, which will enable consensus among stakeholders and positive engagement from the local community. - Municipalities and local community as main actors. - Cultural activities developed by the projects become increasingly relevant when these plans and spaces organize “social activities, and the openness and attendance of the site is an engine for the revitalisation” (p. 9) of the local communities. This relates to the local community becoming the most important customer segment as it “benefits from the results, both directly attending the cultural events and shared spaces and indirectly enjoying the positive effect on local 	<p>2007; Aas et al., 2005).</p>		
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				<p>neighbourhoods” (p. 9). This speaks to the “co-creation” of the project.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Achieving self-sustainability meant moving from publicly funded projects to a running independent business. The BM highlights the diversification of business activities in order to reach economic self-sufficiency. 			
<p>A sustainable perspective in wine production for common-good management: The case of Fontanafredda biological “reserve”</p>	<p>Fontanafredda, Italy</p>	<p>Single case study</p>	<p>Qualitative study. Primary data was collected from in-depth interviews and direct observations. Secondary data was collected from documentation from the company (advertising material and other</p>	<p>“Considering food as commons” (p. 260) requires a wider understanding of the context where the product is elaborated, by integrating notions of traditions and innovations in the management of the common, and their link to a certain area. The authors of the paper analyse how sustainability is crucial in maintaining and assigning value to a common good, using the case of the Italian winery Fontanafredda as a case study. It is argued that “a sustainable strategy for common-good management could improve the competitive advantage of a winery” (p. 260).</p> <p>The focus of the research revolves around the following RQ: “using a sustainable approach as a driver for innovation in wine production and considering wine as a common good, how is it possible to manage the production in respect of a sustainable development of the whole territory?” (p. 262).</p>	<p>Tragedy of the commons (Hardin, 1968; Ostrom, 2015)</p>	<p>Cantino V.; Giacosa E.; Cortese D.</p>	<p>British Food Journal</p>

			internet sources).	<p>Fontanafredda is a historic winery in Piedmont, established in 1858 by Vittorio Emanuele II. Historic transformations of the company, including a bankruptcy in the 1930s and a change in ownership in 2008, by the owners of Eataly, the winery is now focused on a sustainability strategy. Fontanafredda produces organic wine and employs innovative sustainable techniques such as eco-friendly pest control and solar energy. An example that symbolizes these efforts is the Vino Libero project, producing wine free of fertilisers and herbicides, as well as a high percentage of organic sulphites. In this project a fourth of the company's suppliers are involved, defining the wider array of stakeholders included in the sustainability strategy of Fontanafredda.</p> <p>The authors highlight the preservation of traditions as well as innovative strategies that have led to the current sustainability strategy of the company. On the one hand, Fontanafredda preserves traditional wine-making practices and recipes, while using historic structures. The company maintains its name, rooted in the territory and the workers keep close ties to the wine-making processes by living in historic structures nearby. On the other hand, adaptations to sustainability demands have pushed the wine makers to focus on, for example, organic certifications and wastewater</p>			
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				<p>recovery processes. Furthermore, Fontanafredda invests on external consultants and R&D to develop their reach and equipment and techniques that enhance traditional methods.</p> <p>These efforts, tradition and innovation, are balanced and provide Fontanafredda with a sustainable competitive advantage. These crystallize in recognitions such as “Fontanafredda [being] the largest organic-certified company in Piedmont”.</p>			
<p>Balancing Indigenous Values Through Diverse Economies: A Case Study of Māori Eco-tourism</p>	<p>Otago Peninsula, New Zealand</p>	<p>Single case study</p>	<p>Qualitative multi-method approach, with a kaupapa Māori framework (participatory and culturally safe methodology ensured the integration of Māori</p>	<p>The Blue Penguins Pukekura (BPP) serves as a case study to enlighten indigenous entrepreneurship ventures in the field of eco-tourism, with a key focus on indigenous rights to their land, history and culture, and a sustainable hybrid business model.</p> <p>BPP’s goal is to contribute to the preservation and care of the endemic species of little blue penguins, or kororā. BPP provides “nightly wildlife tours (p. 484), and it is situated in a nature reserve, where many protected species coexist. The land ancestrally belongs to the Ngāi Tahu people, but it went through a history of land appropriation, and “has yet to be resolved due to ongoing legal complications” (p. 486). In BPP’s operations it is also deeply engrained the cultural heritage of its people and</p>	<p><i>No clear theoretical framework.</i></p> <p>Diverse economies framework (e.g. Gibson-Graham, 2006) & hybrid economy framework (e.g. Altman, 2009).</p>	<p>Amoamo M.; Ruckstuhl K.; Ruwhiu D.</p>	<p>Tourism Planning and Development</p>

			<p>perspectives, with the research findings reviewed and approved by participants to maintain relational accountability). Semi-structured interviews, review of publicly available material on the venture.</p>	<p>their relationship to their territory. Through tourism, the venture retells its own history raising awareness of its land and people. Beyond these activities, BPP also engages in conservation projects, such as planting native trees, predator control and sustainability of the business model aimed at protecting the penguin population and their habitat.</p> <p>Māori values are intrinsic to the business model of the ecotourism venture, such as <i>tiaki</i>, notion that refers to “putting on limits” (p. 489), and implies “environmental trusteeship [...] also, a notion that sees limiting growth as a desirable economic objective because, as our interviewee noted, “the business model could collapse because the penguin population collapses”” (p. 489). Other key Māori values engrained in BPP are <i>manaakitanga</i> (hospitality) and <i>kaitiakitanga</i> (environmental stewardship).</p> <p>The paper analyses the evolution of BPP’s organizational structure and depicts the venture as an exemplary case of the diverse economies’ framework (e.g. Gibson-Graham, 2006). The findings define BPP’ business model as a hybrid one, by exploring (1) the transformation of the venture into a partnership with the Royal Albatross Centre, while maintaining separate governance models, and (2) the economic development for the local community enabled by the venture while protecting the bottom-up Māori governance (which was not</p>			
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				without authority issues among themselves), their values (collectivity, hospitality, land, network of familial relationships...).			
Culinary attributes and technological utilization as drivers of place authenticity and branding: the case of Vascitour, Naples	Naples, Italy	Single case study	Qualitative exploratory approach. Analysis of online communication channel (website, blog, social media...), interviews and tourists' feedback on online platforms (Facebook & TripAdvisor).	<p>Co-creation of a city's brand is highly dependent on authentic experiences such as gastronomic experiences, where the local attributes of a place are elemental. The paper investigates the case study of Vascitour, a tour operator in Naples established in 2015 aiming at offering authentic, immersive travel experiences through providing services in three areas: stays in traditional vascio houses, guided tours in less well-known areas of the city and dining with Neapolitan families. Through such immersions, the tourists engage more directly with local communities, who are active in retelling their stories and sharing their culture.</p> <p>The findings highlight the relevance of gastronomy: "leverage food as a way to create the opportunity to let tourists interact with the community, such as residents and shop owners" (p. 14). This explains the engagement of various types of tourists, and the complexity of tourism in Naples, which combines tradition and modernity. The authors investigate the process of the experiences. For instance, engaging in family-like dinners with locals, not only do tourists develop social bonds, but they acquire a "coherent, organic image" of the 'place', and thus, go on to share the experience though</p>	No clear framework. Concepts related to place-based theory, from a branding perspective. Place-based theory (e.g. place as a brand: Kavaratzi, 2005; place as a 'social bond': Ramkisson et al., 2012)	Vrontis D.; Basile G.; Tani M.; Thrassou A.	Journal of Place Management and Development

				<p>review channels and platforms, strengthening the image of Naples.</p> <p>The paper provides insights on a community-driven governance model, as local stakeholders become key in the branding of Naples, further enriching a place-based identity.</p>			
<p>From communism to market: business models and governance in heritage conservation in Poland</p>	<p>Poland</p>	<p>Multiple case study</p>	<p>Intensive research: “in-depth examination of a limited number of cases to grasp the intrinsic complexity of political and social phenomena” (p. 792). Data from documents (promotional and historical material</p>	<p>The interplay between business models and the governance of heritage sites has an impact on conservation efforts, as well as the functionality and longevity of historical buildings. The paper investigates three cases studies in Lower Silesia, Poland: “Ksiaz Castle, the Shrine of Our Lady of Grace Abbey, and the historic palaces located in Jelenia Gora Valley” (p. 788). The authors examine how privatization and decentralization following the fall of communism transformed heritage management. “The three sites shared a similar transition from a situation of decay before the fall of communism to improved conservation in recent years” (p. 793).</p> <p>Three business models are identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Theme Park</i>: a commercially driven business model, in the Ksiaz Castle. Owned by the municipality of Walbrzych and managed by a private company under a public contract. The goal is to maximize revenue through tourism visits. Minimal cultural events 	<p><i>No clear theoretical framework.</i></p> <p>Governance theory, decentralization and state withdrawal (Rhodes, 1996, 2007). Multi-actor governance (Osborne, 2010; Pierre, 2000); PPP (Bovaird & Tizzard, 2009). Business Model analysis in</p>	<p>Bonini Baraldi S.; Ferri P.</p>	<p>Journal of Management and Governance</p>

			<p>on the sites), semi-structured interviews and observations.</p>	<p>dedicated to the local community. The site's heritage value is secondary to its role as an entertainment venue, reflecting its marginal importance in Poland's national identity.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Heritage Reserve</i>: Supported by donations and public funding, exemplified by the Abbey. Managed by the Dioceses of Legnica. EU funding and income from religious tourism services. Focus is on heritage conservation. Accessibility for pilgrims as well as tourists is prioritized. - <i>Adaptative Reuse</i>: repurposing a cultural heritage site through private donations, as seen in the Jelenia Gora palaces. Governed by a mix of private ownership, public agencies and non-profit foundations. Decentralization has allowed transferred responsibility to private actors, while public oversight is maintained. <p>Overall, the study shows the transition towards a decentralized market economy in post-communist Poland, which applies to the management and functionality of cultural heritage sites. Both in the theme park and the adaptive reuse models, the financial sustainability of the site takes priority over</p>	<p>the field of heritage (e.g. Zan et al., 2015)</p>		
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				<p>cultural preservation. The paper highlights the benefits of decentralization and private engagement in the management of the sites, as this has fostered conservation efforts. However, the analysis suggests an inherent tension between economic and cultural underlying causes.</p>			
<p>An examination of a social tourism business in Granada, Nicaragua</p>	<p>Granada, Nicaragua</p>	<p>Single Case study</p>	<p>Multi-method research. Qualitative research. Data collected from in-depth interviews, direct field observations, photographic documentation and analysis of secondary data (annual</p>	<p>Considering identified consequences of tourism in less economically developed (LEDCs), such as the reliance on “foreign skills and finance” that lead to “much of the earnings can leak out into other economies” (p. 1179), other business models aim at creating “added value to individuals, communities and the environment” (p. 1180). Social enterprises in tourism focus on developing bottom-up approaches, where the management of such initiatives stem from the residents ‘at home’.</p> <p>The authors choose Hotel con Corazón (Hotel with Heart), in Granada, Nicaragua to exemplify a successful business model canvas of a social enterprise. The enterprise is a boutique hotel that reinvests all profits into local educational programs. Founded in 2008 by two Dutch social entrepreneurs, the hotel’s aim is to tackle systemic issues in the field of education in Nicaragua, and it does so by promoting environmental (seeking energy efficiency and sourcing local supplies, reducing its</p>	<p><i>No clear framework.</i> Uses BMC for social enterprises by Qastharin (2014), which builds on Osterwalder and Pigneur’s (2010) framework. Concepts of Social Enterprises in Tourism (e.g. Hall and Kirkpatrick, 2005).</p>	<p>Franzidis A.</p>	<p>Tourism Review</p>

			<p>reports & web content). Triangulation of data.</p>	<p>carbon footprint) and socially (reinvesting profits on local education) sustainable tourism.</p> <p>The findings present the BMC of the hotel, based on Qastharin's (2014) model, a framework adapted for social enterprises, which adds on Osterwalder and Pigneur's (2010) framework by adding two extra layers: impact and measurements; and mission. The model also identifies co-creators of value and beneficiaries of the BM.</p> <p>The revenue streams of Hotel con Corazón, coming from accommodation, dining and tours, is redirected to local NGOs whose efforts are based on the enhancing of local education. The hotel employs local residents, who are trained by the enterprise. Furthermore, partnerships with local craftsmen are part of the BM, as the hotel sells their products to tourists. Key to the BMC is the measurements of social impact: in 2015, 284 students from rural areas were supported, seven teachers received funding, as well as several employees who aimed at going to university. Other parameters related to grades and the reduction of economic leakage outside of the community are monitored by the SE and analysed as success KPIs.</p> <p>The hotel presents a case study of a successful SE, in aligning financial and social purposes.</p>			
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<p>Tourism to serve culture: the evolution of an Aboriginal tourism business model in Australia</p>	<p>Kimberley, Australia</p>	<p>Exploratory single case study</p>	<p>Qualitative research. Data collected from “publicly available documents, websites, promotional materials and conference presentations about the venture, in-depth interviews with key informants during on-country visits to their main base at Wijn-gadda</p>	<p>Indigenous people-led tourism enterprises are presented as examples in the literature of culturally appropriate business models. A key difference between non-indigenous and indigenous business models is, especially in tourism, that the essence of the BM lays on the cultural heritage of the community and its interconnectedness to nature.</p> <p>The article looks at a tourism venture and its evolution towards a full ownership of the enterprise by Dambimangari Traditional Owners. The results present three phases of the development of the Indigenous tourism BM, from 1995 to 2017:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Phase 1: non-indigenous fishing charter business. Traditional Owners leased part of the Dambeemangari land for non-indigenous operator to run fishing tours. The cultural indigenous theme was limited, as well as the social or economic return to the Traditional Owners. - Phase 2: creation of a joint enterprise, and initiatives such as cultural storytelling or Indigenous art sales. Skill development for the Traditional Owners’ community. Shared infrastructures, although increase in tensions between Indigenous and non-Indigenous operations over control and ownership. - Phase 3: fully owned by Traditional Owners “Dambimangari Traditional Tour Guides”. 	<p>Yunus et al.’s (2010) social business model provides the framework for the case analysis.</p> <p>Culture conservation economy (e.g. Hill et al., 2008) and indigenous entrepreneurship in tourism (e.g. Weiler & Black, 2015).</p>	<p>Scherrer P.</p>	<p>Tourism Review</p>
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		<p>Bard (Freshwater Cove); on-site observations; and follow-up phone and email communications” (p. 668).</p> <p>Approach to the data: researchers (non-Indigenous) recognise their privilege and engage in a constant process of self-reflection (Brown et al., 2010;</p>	<p>Independence from non-Indigenous fishing charter business model.</p> <p>Along its development, the Dambimangari Aboriginal Corporation (DAC), with increasing representation from Traditional Owners’ interests, enhanced its relationship with local administration bodies, such as the Kimberley Land Council and state government grant programs. The increased control over the operations by the Traditional Owners fostered recognition from organizations such as the Western Australian Indigenous Tourism Operators Council (WAITOC), which also provided financial support.</p> <p>Changes in its governance and ownership are highlighted as well as the evolution across various characteristics of the enterprise, such as its value proposition, profit equation or depth of indigenous theme (p. 674). Overall, the findings highlight social benefits including intergenerational cultural transfer, employment opportunities, and community resilience.</p>			
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			McIntosh, 1988)				
Social entrepreneurship and tourism in Cambodia: advancing community engagement	Cambodia	Qualitative case study	Data collected from a database on Social Entrepreneurship in Cambodia. From that dataset, 25 stakeholders from the tourism sector were invited to an extended focus group. The second part of the data collection process was	<p>Social enterprises that engage with local communities have been found to have a stronger impact in development goals. Taking as a case study the Cambodian field of tourism-based social enterprises (TSEs), the authors ask, “what approaches to community participation in tourism development are being encouraged by social entrepreneurship in Cambodia?” (p. 817).</p> <p>The paper lays out a classification of the levels of community engagement in TSEs in the literature (see p. 819) and build on the argument that there is a “reconciliation of environmental conservation and local livelihood needs through stakeholder collaboration” (p. 819) in TSEs that are based on high or very high levels of community engagement. The literature also highlights the benefits of increasing community participation in TSEs for their long-term sustainability and for addressing challenges such as income leakage.</p> <p>The results find three types of TSEs, based on their level of community engagement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cash cow: leveraging tourism activities to redirect profits to NGOs. Levels of 	<p><i>No clear theoretical framework.</i></p> <p>Rather, builds on existing literature on social entrepreneurship in tourism and the challenges and opportunities this creates (e.g. Burns, 1999). Community-based tourism, or inclusive tourism (e.g. Sheldon and Daniele, 2017). Classic conservationist approach (Carter, 2006)</p>	Dahles H.; Khieng S.; Verver M.; Manders I.	Journal of Sustainable Tourism

		<p>based on 27 semi-structured interviews, on site observations with 16 Tourism-based Social Enterprises (TSEs) and other stakeholders.</p>	<p>community engagement remain low, as the locals are given little agency in the development of initiatives and are rather the “beneficiaries”. Here, financial gains are prioritized over a shared governance structure. Beneficial gains for the communities are, for instance, employment and income. Consequences of such models are, for instance, the lack of community empowerment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community empowerment: this model utilizes tourism to provide self-sustainability to the locals. Some initiatives are fostering locals to develop their own tourism-related micro-enterprises. Some barriers to this model are systemic lack of financial education of the locals and a high reliance on external funding for the maintenance of the enterprises. - Inclusive business model: here social values are to be at the core of tourism enterprises. This means, in practical terms, initiatives such as co-creation and ownership within local communities. For instance, tour operators that employ and train young residents and offer them promotion programmes to become shareholders of the company. Another example is the diversification of income purposed to local farmers, which can 			
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				develop eco-tourism activities such as farm tours or workshops. Challenges of such model stem from its lack of scalability potential or difficulty of replicating the model in a variety of markets.			
Institutional Voids and Business Model Innovation: How Grassroots Social Businesses Advance Deprived Communities in Emerging Economies	Brazil	Qualitative Single Case Study	Qualitative research: primary data from semi-structured interviews and secondary data from social media interactions, press articles and reports on the company's activities	<p>Institutional voids, characteristic from developing economies, are defined as “prevailing institutional conditions that disturb the functioning of markets, enhancing the likelihood of opportunism (including corruption), excessive rents to a few actors (reducing entrepreneurship) and market power (discouraging competition)” (p. 314). Local entrepreneurs that have been identified as potential challengers of such dynamics have the potential to bring about social value. In illuminating how these business models create value and challenge institutional voids, the authors bring the case study of a grassroots social business in Brazilian favelas, under the pseudonym of Alpha. Alpha’s aim is to “fight obesity – a serious social problem caused by poor-quality diet – by offering freshly made salads at affordable prices and employing favela dwellers. Alpha was nurtured by the social incubator Yunus Negócios Sociais, one of a network of organizations created by Muhammad Yunus (the Yunus Group), the founder of the Grameen Bank” (p. 315).</p> <p>The results inform, first, about the business model of Alpha. This is based on integrating favela</p>	<p>Institutional theory (e.g. North, 1990). Specifically, institutional voids and consequences in market development & participation (e.g. Mair & Marti, 2009).</p> <p>Social entrepreneurship in Emerging economies (e.g. Yunus et al., 2010; Alvord et al. (2004).</p>	Colovic A.; Schruof-fenegger M.	Management and Organization Review

			<p>residents at every stage of the value chain. Residents are cooks, delivery workers and franchisees. Sourcing also comes from local farmers. Main customers of the business model include residents, nurseries, schools and wealthier clients from outside the favelas.</p> <p>Second, Alpha's business model directly tackles institutional voids and creates social value. By creating a local network of actors engaged in the activities of the business, the market functioning and the business ecosystem of the area directly benefits. By providing employment and training, the levels of economic inclusion also increase. Improvements on the public image of marginalized communities and connections with communities outside the favelas also reduce institutional voids.</p> <p>Third, the authors develop a theoretical model by "linking innovative social business models, institutional voids, and social value creation" (p. 338), based on eight mechanisms: four of them (legitimizing, upgrading and building cognitive capacity, assigning multiple roles and empowering) address institutional voids and create social values, in contrast to two mechanisms that solely impact on institutional voids (orchestrating <i>and</i> developing local business networks), and the remaining two mechanisms that create social value but do</p>	<p>Social business model innovation (e.g. Amit & Zott, 2010)</p>		
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				not enhance institution conditions (building territorial identity and boundary spanning) (see on p. 339).			
The village as a social entrepreneur: Balancing conservation and livelihoods	Sikkim, India	Single case study	<p>Qualitative approach, grounded theory.</p> <p>Primary data was collected through a combination of participant observation, semi-structured interviews, and group discussions. The researchers stayed at the</p>	<p>Ecotourism provides a solution for the improvement of livelihoods in rural areas. Ecotourism can also be a source of supplementary income. An example of this is the model of community-based home-stay arrangement (p. 100). However, issues such as its financial viability, as well as the consequences in social distribution of value and its compatibility with the natural and cultural contexts remain a question. The paper uses the case study of two adjoining villages in Sikkim, India, which have adopted this ecotourism model. The aim of the paper is to understand its business model and raise awareness over the inherent tension between “environmental sustainability and financial success” (p. 100).</p> <p>The two villages in Sikkim that comprises the case study have developed a business model offering to tourists stays at family homes, experiencing traditional culture and being surrounded by nature. This emerged as an adaptative response from a drop in the availability of cardamom, the town’s main crop and source of income. Residents collaborated with a local NGO (ECOSS) to establish ecotourism as a sustainable alternative to harmful economic practices like illegal logging. ECOSS</p>	No theoretical framework. Concepts used include community-based home-stay ecotourism models (e.g. Schaeyvens, 1999)	Sarkar R.; Sinha A.	Tourism Management Perspectives

		<p>homestays and participated in the local activities. Secondary data systems from demographic reports and project-related documents.</p>	<p>helped residents to develop skills and resources and was involved in the coordination process among the villages: "ECOSS's role was limited to the marketing of the villages as an ecotourism destination and in developing minimal ability to provide clean and hygienic toilet facilities, simple food and comfortable rooms. Allocation and pricing of resources and actual investment for provision of tourism facilities was left to the villagers" (p. 103).</p> <p>Other activities developed by residents included traditional musical shows for the guests. However, there were issues regarding the engagement of children in the shows, as they participated out of obligation to their parents.</p> <p>Challenges are highlighted by the authors, such as the disparities among the two villages, the lack of infrastructure to host large groups, the lack of funds to do needed renovations or consistent pricing for tourists. Nonetheless, the ecotourism activities reduced illegal logging activities.</p> <p>The results develop on the ecotourism business model. The authors argue that there was not one. This meant that there was a lack of agreement among residents on the allocation of</p>			
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				<p>responsibilities or the design of an enterprise itself to run the different tourism activities. The issue stem from the lack of coordination among independent households, which led to other related challenges such as the marketing of the area as an ecotourism destination, the governance of the model, or the pricing strategies, due to the lack of collected data from the tourism demand side.</p> <p>The paper concludes on the lack of clarity of the business model, by emphasizing its challenges for replicability until further developed. This further increases the chances of residents shifting to the exploitation of natural resources, as a consequence of the lack of resilience of the ecotourism model.</p>			
Rural tourism management: Gap between expected and reality	Village of Gubuglakah Malang Indonesia	Single Case Study	Qualitative approach	Rural tourism management, according to Indonesian public tourism guidelines as a means of community empowerment, identifies three distinct clusters that vary based on the location of tourism interests: in one concrete village, where surrounding villages participate and benefit from the economic activities generated; a tourism attraction, linking surrounding villages, as these provide various tourism services; or the area that encompasses various villages, having the capacity to distribute economic benefits (p. 281).	<i>No clear theoretical framework.</i> Draws from rural tourism management concepts. Literature on the development of rural tourism through local	Sudarmiati; Handayati P.; Soetjipto B.E.; Hidayat R.; Bukhori I.	International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research

			<p>Taking this framework as a point of departure, the researchers analyse the management of rural tourism of the selected case study, the rural village of Gubugklakah, Malang. Since the number of visitors remains relatively low, despite the natural attractions near the village, the authors seek to analyse the management of rural tourism in Gubugklakah and identify the factors contributing to this gap between expectations and reality.</p> <p>Gubugklakah is near to Mount Bromo and the Cuban Pelangi waterfall, two major natural tourist attractions (p. 284). Furthermore, agricultural activities with ecotourism potential, such as apple picking, are among some of the possibilities of the area.</p> <p>The findings highlight several challenges that hinder effective tourism management in the town. First, a lack among stakeholders (the head of the village, tourism providers and local business owners) leads to inefficiencies in rural tourism management.</p> <p>Second, although there exist national guidelines on rural tourism management, these lack local legal regulation on tourism, and so “everything related to the rights and obligations of the</p>	<p>community engagement and active public policy initiatives (e.g. Panyik et al., 2011)</p>		
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				<p>community in the management of the tourist village has not been explicitly regulated” (p. 285).</p> <p>Third, there is an overall lack of managerial skills among involved tourism providers, hindering strategic planning, marketing and partnerships with travel agencies.</p> <p>The study suggests that improving tourism in Gubugklakah requires enhancing human resource capacity through training, workshops, and collaboration with tourism experts. Additionally, integrating tourism offerings with neighbouring villages through package tours could provide a more attractive experience for visitors. Establishing village tourism regulations would also help create a structured approach to managing and promoting the destination effectively.</p>			
Place-based business models for resilient local economies: Cases from Italian slow food, agritourism and the <i>albergo diffuso</i>	Italy	Multiple-case studies	<p><i>No clear methodology.</i></p> <p>“This is a conceptual paper with case studies from qualitative data and</p>	Place-based business models leverage their geographical, cultural, and social contexts for value creation. As the authors state, “entrepreneurs use highly context-specific strategies and linkages to a ‘sense of place’ as sources of value creation” (p. 113). These models enhance local resilience and sustainability, particularly in food, tourism, and agritourism, where regional identity and authenticity are key to economic success.	Place-based business models & value creation though the notion of “sense of place” (e.g. Williams et al., 1992; f Thompson 1967; McKeever et	Di Gregorio D.	Journal of Enterprising Communities

			<p>external sources” (p. 113). Drawing from 4 case studies.</p>	<p>The paper examines three Italian cases of place-based business models: Slow Food enterprises (Coop Italia and Eataly), agritourism (Spannocchia), and the albergo diffuso (Sextantio), illustrating how they generate value and support local economies.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Slow Food enterprises integrate small-scale producers into larger markets. Coop Italia, Italy’s largest supermarket chain, partners with producer cooperatives to co-brand regional food products, ensuring high quality while distributing value along the supply chain. It also supports the Ark of Taste’s Presidia initiative, “a certified collection of distinctive typical food products, enabling a transition from “local production for local consumers” to “local production for distant consumers” (p. 119) which was launched by the Slow Food Organization and supported by Coop. Eataly, with its hybrid supermarket-restaurant-theme park format, organizes food by region and educates consumers on provenance. While successful internationally, the model risks “trivializing authentic cultural resources” (p. 120). - Agritourism blends farming with hospitality, offering tourists an authentic agricultural experience (p. 120). While different models exist, those that fully integrate agriculture and tourism best capture a sense of place (p. 121). Spannocchia (Tuscany) has fostered 	<p>al., 2015); and terroir (Bérard and Marchenay, 2008; d Trubek, 2008); Institutional voids (Luporini and Parigi, 1996).</p>		
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				<p>the revival of the <i>cinta senese pig</i>, an endangered breed, creating a high-end market for its meat, which is raised under strict free-range and dietary standards. Spannocchia also produces wine and olive oil, selling through direct and external channels. Its tourism services (lodging, hiking, and education) ensure that visitor revenues directly sustain traditional farming and landscape conservation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The <i>albergo diffuso</i> model of cultural tourism, pioneered by Sextantio, revitalizes declining historic villages by transforming them into dispersed hotels. Unlike conventional tourism, this model preserves the existing urban fabric, integrating hospitality services across multiple restored buildings. Sextantio's success lies in its commitment to authenticity, incorporating local materials, traditional crafts, and historical narratives into the guest experience. <p>By integrating local identity into their core strategies, businesses like Coop Italia, Eataly, Spannocchia, and Sextantio demonstrate that regional distinctiveness can be a competitive advantage, though challenges remain in scaling up while maintaining authenticity.</p>			
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<p>Marketing culture through locally-grown products: The case of the Fransaskoisie Terroir products</p>	<p>Saskatchewan, Canada</p>	<p>Single-case study</p>	<p><i>No clear methodology.</i> A survey is mentioned: "Following earlier research, the objective of our survey was to collect detailed information about how to successfully implement the Terroir concept in the Canadian province of Saskatchewan" (p. 91).</p>	<p>Food marketing increasingly intersects with cultural identity, particularly in regions seeking to maintain economic sustainability through value-added agricultural products. This case study examines the <i>future possibilities</i> of implementing <i>Terroir</i> concept within Saskatchewan's Fransaskoisie community, a minority French-speaking population. By linking locally grown specialty food products with cultural heritage, this initiative aims to address rural economic decline while capitalizing on consumer demand for authenticity.</p> <p>The findings highlight that Saskatchewan's agricultural sector faces significant challenges, including a shrinking rural population and reliance on raw product exports. Despite these issues, there is a growing demand for high-quality, regionally branded foods, offering an opportunity to shift towards value-added production. The Terroir model emphasizes branding products based on geographic and cultural uniqueness.</p> <p>To implement this model, the Fransaskoisie community should establish an organization that supports producers in branding, marketing, and exporting their goods under a unified identity. The authors propose a "detailed organization model, a three-year budget and measurable metrics of success guarantee sustainability are presented" (p. 92).</p>	<p>Terroir, place-based approach (Blay-Palmer and Donald, 2006; Sims, 2009)</p> <p>Creative capitalism in the food industry (Hemphill, 2010)</p>	<p>Charlebois S.; Mackay G.</p>	<p>Problems and Perspectives in Management</p>
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				<ul style="list-style-type: none">- The organization plan is built on the premise of achieving value-added production benefits for the producers of Saskatchewan, by leveraging the Fransaskoisie identity through product branding and marketing. The authors emphasize the need of forming strong partnerships (with media organizations, retailers, such as specialty food stores, sponsors, cultural organizations and local producers) and enhancing visibility through workshops, conferences, and expert panels for producers.- The three-year budget is essential to transitioning from public funding to self-sufficiency. Key insights are producer contributions and membership fees, strategic retailing and licensing fees, as well as diversifying revenue streams, by creating agritourism activities.- Metrics across three areas aim to guarantee sustainability of the business model. In the economic and business growth metrics, the authors suggest keeping track of the number of producers engaged, the revenue increases for farmers and the number of retail partnerships along the years. In understanding the development of product and branding awareness, metrics tracking the consumer awareness or event participation can			
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				<p>suggest developments in this area. Lastly, investigating the sources of revenue (public vs private) as well as brand and certification growth can capture the sustainability of the organization in the long term.</p>			
<p>Place-based network organizations and embedded entrepreneurial learning: Emerging paths to sustainability</p>	<p>Torre Guaceto, South-east Coast of Italy</p>	<p>Single-case study</p>	<p>Qualitative approach and triangulation of data: official reports, press reports, interviews, field observation.</p>	<p>This study examines how entrepreneurial learning facilitates the sustainable transition of place-based enterprises in their management and exploitation of “commons”, or natural resources. The place-based enterprises can emerge as a key social actor in the management of place-based common resources, vis-à-vis classical economic theory, which places this responsibility in the government (p. 504).</p> <p>The paper aims at merging two theoretical approaches to analyse entrepreneurial learning as a driver behind sustainable management of the commons: the adaptive management view and Lachmann’s entrepreneurial theory. The results develop a six-step model to describe this process and use a case study on the fishing enterprises in an Italian marine protected area (MPA) (p. 504) of Torre Guaceto, Italy, to test their model.</p> <p>The Torre Guaceto MPA has a history of adaptation to various public policy efforts to protect the</p>	<p>Challenging the use of RBV and Schumpeterian approaches to organizational learning and competitive advantage. Draws on: “the adaptive management view, on the one side, and Lachmann’s view of entrepreneurship, on the other side” (p. 505) to study a place-based</p>	<p>Cantino V.; Devalle A.; Cortese D.; Ricciardi F.; Longo M.</p>	<p>International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research</p>

			<p>marine ecosystem from overfishing and environmental degradation. Initially, local fishermen resisted the MPA's regulations, which started in the 1990s' and strictly were adopted in 2000, as fishing bans threatened their livelihoods. In 2002, social dialogue begun, and the fragility of the ecosystem was highlighted to the fishermen by a scientific group, which enabled the co-creation of solutions. Through adaptive co-management, they collaborated with scientists and policymakers to develop a sustainable fishing model.</p> <p>From 2005, when the fishing ban was removed. The MPA had led to ecological recovery, increased fish stocks, and a more profitable and sustainable fishing industry. A sustainable fishing protocol was developed currently in place that allows fishers to fish in a designated part of the Torre Guaceto MPA. The area serves as a scientific monitoring site, where fishers contribute to ongoing data collection, ensuring that fishing activities do not harm the ecosystem. As put by the authors "the fishermen became MPA rangers, and their collaboration and surveillance proved very effective" (p. 12). Other advancements towards the sustainable management and exploitation of the commons are the creation of the Community of Organic Producers and Fishermen of the Reserve of Torre Guaceto in 2006, the first and only recognition by the BioFish</p>	<p>enterprises management of the commons.</p> <p>(Lachmann, 1970); e.g. (Allan and Curtis, 2005; Wyborn, 2015)</p> <p>place-based enterprise, introduced by Shrivastava and Kennelly (2013), and intersection with green entrepreneurship (e.g. Kirkwood and Walton, 2010).</p>		
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				<p>label in Italy to the group of fishermen of the MPA, or the Blue Flag Award by the UN.</p> <p>The story of the MPA is synthesized and theorized by the authors through the following stages of entrepreneurial learning (1) initial resistance, (2) opportunity recognition, (3) adaptive learning, (4) institutional change, (5) experimentation, and (6) social legitimation.</p> <p>Drawing from Lachmann, entrepreneurial ignorance led (the initial resistance of the fishermen due to their lack of awareness on the area's environmental risks) to creativity and opportunity identification (then another approach to policy co-creation is adopted). Entrepreneurs actively engage in governance processes. On the other hand, adaptive co-management theory is useful to explain the adaptive learning cycles, based on institutional evolution and environmental sustainability.</p>			
Business Model Evolution and Entrepreneurial Adaptation of Festivals: The Case of	Chile	Single-case study	Qualitative approach. Archival documents and semi-	Cultural organizations engage with and adapt to their sociopolitical environmental. Festivals, for instance, "respond to various types of local stakeholders and to their emerging and changing demands" (p. 77). In doing so, changes in their business models reflect these developments. The paper examines the evolution of the business model	<i>No clear framework.</i> BM "renewal" (e.g. Svejenova et al., 2010; Eyring et al.,	Serge Poisson-de Haro, Alvaro Espejo, Ignasi Martí	INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ARTS MANAGEMENT

Santiago a Mil			structured interviews.	<p>of <i>Santiago a Mil</i>, one of South America’s most prominent theatre festivals, from its inception in 1994 to its current form.</p> <p>The festival emerged in post-dictatorial Chile as a private initiative to revitalize cultural expression. Over nearly three decades, the festival has transformed from a small-scale event into an internationally recognized performing arts platform. “The objective of this study is to advance our understanding of how the design and implementation of business models of performing arts festivals can generate spaces for social transformation and positively impact not just economic, but also social and environmental, factors” (p. 77).</p> <p>The results identify four key phases in the business model development:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emergence (1994-2000): the limited funding for the arts stagnated the development of the festival in its initial stage, therefore, most of its funding was private. Key at the initial stage was the founders’ entrepreneurial spirit, and personal networks. - Growth (2001-2006): the festival included its first international performances. The Fundación Teatro a Mil, a non-profit foundation, was established, with the aim of formalizing 	<p>2011), and its adaptation to a “business model for a performing arts organization” (Poisson-de Haro and Montpetit, 2012).</p> <p>Cultural entrepreneurs (e.g. Jones et al. 2016; Lounsbury et al. 2019).</p>		
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				<p>the governance of the festival and ensuring financial transparency. Partnerships with private sponsors (e.g. Minera Escondida, operated by BHP) and local governments enabled further funding and accessibility through the staging of performances in public spaces.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wide Recognition: (2007-2019): increased government support and institutionalization of the festival as Chile’s main theatre event, transitioning towards mass public participation. - Social Connection (2020-Present): in response to the 2019 Chilean protests, the festival adapted its programming to reflect the political and social concerns of the moment “calling this new version an “emergency Santiago a Mil” (p. 88). The festival focused on social media engagement and developed discussion platforms that enabled public debate (“cabildo”) (see p. 88). <p>The case of Santiago a Mil is portrayed as “<i>prefigurative</i> [emphasis added] (Gibson-Graham 2006) in that they promote positive, affirmative engagement with certain practices, anticipating “here and now” the society they wish to create – in this case, one that is more equal, fair and inclusive” (p. 91).</p>			
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